

Wind Resource Parametrisation and Power Harvesting Estimation using AWERA - the Airborne Wind Energy Resource Analysis tool

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I hereby declare that this thesis was formulated by myself and that no sources or tools other than those cited were used.

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Date

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Signature

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Introduction

In recent years the importance of renewable energy sources such as solar, wind and others has become central in public discussion on the future of energy supply. The recent developments pertaining to the climate crisis, especially droughts and floods are found to be exceedingly regular and of extreme extent, even in the traditionally less impacted northern European region.

From a more political point of view, renewable energy provides means for more energy independence, especially from oil and gas, which has become much more relevant in recent months. The aim for 100% renewable energies in the energy supply is thus no question of 'if' but more of 'when' and 'how'. Supplying 100% renewable energy requires the sources to provide continuous, dependable and easily dispatchable energy sources.

The most abundant sources, solar and wind, are harvested using solar panels and conventional wind turbines, producing cheap energy but they are impacted strongly by the volatility of the resources. A very strong constraint is on harvesting solar energy, as there is no sun at night. However solar energy is still the most prominent renewable source, in part because it has such high potential, especially for decentralised harvesting.

The current transition to renewable energy in Germany is focused mostly on the electrical power, with a share of now 41.1%. Including other energy dependent sectors such as heating, cooling and transportation, the share of renewable drops to 19.7% [2], such that strong sector coupling is proposed to electrify all energy consuming sectors.

Due to the volatility of most renewable sources and the large energy demand, it is essential to combine various renewable energy sources, making lows and highs of the available power complement each other, leading to an optimal energy system as described in [3].

More stability is reached in these models by storing power during highs and draining such storage when more energy is needed than produced, using either standard battery technology or so-called power-to-X approaches.

Using Airborne Wind Energy (AWE) is proposed to provide continuous power production by harvesting strong and continuous high-altitude winds using tethered flying kites, thus very continuously contributing to the energy system. Power is harvested either by the wind pulling on the tether or using small turbines mounted on the flying device. Small scale AWE systems could be used to replace fuel generators in very remote areas while large scale systems could be used in wind farms in combination with solar farms, possibly making the ground use more efficient. Evaluation of AWE wind parks is already an important part in current AWE research [4]. AWE is on a good way to contribute to the

energy supply, as just last year the first commercial system was launched by SkySails [5] and more pilot releases of other companies, like the Kitepower Falcon [6], are under way.

Quantifying the wind resource available for harvesting with AWE systems and assessing the contribution it can bring to the current and future energy system is important to evaluate the commercial viability of airborne wind energy and to identify optimal harvesting sites. Bechtle et al. [7] performed an analysis on the potentially available wind resource for airborne wind energy, especially focussing on comparison to conventional wind turbines. They describe a strong increase in the wind resource for harvesting airborne wind energy at variable height up to 500 m, focussing only on the wind resource and not the power harvesting. While wind turbines only harvest power at a fixed height, AWE is harvested on a variable height depending on the tether length and elevation, and thus vertical wind profiles giving the wind speeds at a range of heights are needed to evaluate AWE.

Harvested power of an airborne wind energy system is described by simulating the flight path and evaluating the resulting forces, using either detailed dynamic models [8] or alternatively the quasi-steady model approximation by Van der Vlugt et al. [9], as done in this work. Estimating the power production for the complete wind resource in Europe or even worldwide would require a large number of simulations, even using the quasi-steady model. Therefore the wind resource is parametrised, such that the harvesting estimation can be performed on the parametrisation only, as shown by Schelbergen et al. in [10].

The AWERA toolchain aims to combine the AWE assessment and power harvesting evaluation, providing an open source tool for evaluating single sites as well as European and consequently worldwide maps for AWE power harvesting, including validation of the obtained results. Inclusion of AWE in energy systems modelling is seen as an important step for the advancement of this technology. Therefore, special focus is laid on providing time-resolved results to be included in such models. The AWERA toolchain is meant to leave open room for community contribution, e.g. concerning inclusion of current and future AWE kite systems.

In chapter 2, a more comprehensive introduction to the concept of AWE power harvesting as well as the parametrisation and simulation models is given. Chapter 3 focuses on the wind resource analysis, providing updated findings to the previous resource potential study in [7]. Wind resource parametrisation is applied to the European wind resource data of the years 2010 to 2020 in chapter 4, identifying representative wind profile shapes of the wind resource. Chapter 5 continues with estimating the power harvesting for the representation, resulting in the annual energy production for the European map. The most important results are collected in chapter 6, where the combined findings are used to evaluate AWE with respect to potential contribution in the energy system. A final conclusion is drawn in chapter 7.

Concepts and State of Research

Basic concepts surrounding the topic of wind energy and wind resource analysis are introduced. Special focus is placed on airborne wind energy systems and modelling of their power harvesting procedure.

2.1 AWE

Airborne Wind Energy (AWE) refers to harvesting wind energy using flying devices, mostly at higher altitude than normal wind turbines. Increasing the harvesting height and adjusting it to the wind resource give access to strong and more steady high altitude winds. This opens up potential as a complementary wind energy resource to ensure baseload capacity of renewable energy sources. This introduction to AWE is based on the book on Airborne Wind Energy by Ahrens, Diehl and Schmehl [11], and especially on the introductory chapter by Diehl [12].

2.1.1 Principle of Crosswind Power Production

Most Airborne Wind Energy Systems (AWES) consist of a flying device which is connected to the ground station via a tether. The most power can be harvested flying crosswind, where the apparent air speed at the wing v_a is maximised compared to the wind speed v_w at a stationary kite $v_a = v_w$. The aerodynamic lift force is given by

$$F_L = \frac{1}{2} \rho A C_L v_a^2, \quad (2.1)$$

which depends on the air density ρ , the area A of the airfoil and its geometry, described by the lift coefficient C_L .

Thus crosswind flight with v_a larger than the wind speed v_w shows quadratic increase in tether tension. High crosswind flight wind speeds can be maintained by the ambient wind flow and can thus be used either directly or via the tether tension for power harvesting [12].

Both harvesting modes were first described by Miles Loyd in [13], where *lift mode* and *drag mode* describe using the tether tension to pull on a ground based generator and using the high v_a to propel small wind turbines located on the wing, respectively.

This concept is reflected in conventional wind turbines, where the outer 30% of the wings are shown to contribute more than half of the harvested power. Replacing the inner parts of the wings and the

Figure 2.1: Comparison of the outer parts of a conventional wind turbine (left) sweeping the same area as an AWES (right) [12]. Illustration by R. Paelinck

tower by a tether conceptually results in a circularly moving drag mode AWES, illustrated in fig. 2.1. This again shows the potential for strong reduction of material investment in AWES compared to wind turbines, while on the other hand requiring sophisticated control of a unstable flying system compared to a stable turbine [12].

Lyod [13] estimates the generated power P under ideal conditions to be

$$P = \frac{2}{27} \rho A v_w^3 C_L \left(\frac{C_L}{C_D} \right)^2, \quad (2.2)$$

with the wing area A , its lift and drag coefficients C_L and C_D and the wind speed v_w . The lift-to-drag ratio $\frac{C_L}{C_D}$ is an important wing property, also known as the *gliding number* for airplanes. The prototype system used in this work for example has lift and drag coefficients of ($C_L = 0.9, C_D = 0.2$) and ($C_L = 0.2, C_D = 0.1$) flying with powered and depowered steering, respectively.

In a more realistic scenario, the drag coefficient C_D is increased to include the tether drag. Additionally, the mass of AWE device and tether as well as flight controls impact the power that can be harvested by the AWES. Furthermore the electrical power is lower than the harvesting power due to loss during energy conversion in the generator.

A more realistic description would also capture the impact of cosine losses on the maximum power that can be extracted. It depends linearly on the wind speed and aerodynamic force on the wing and is reduced following the cosine of the angle γ in between, ideally corresponding to the angle between wind speed horizontal and tether. This angle is further increased due to gravitational effects, which are shown to be of minor importance compared to the strong tether tension [12]. Considering wind conditions that are not parallel to the ground require and additional projection of the wind direction on the active surface of the wing, introducing an additional cosine squared dependence. The power is therefore reduced with a factor of cosine cubed.

The power that can be harvested results by subtracting the power loss of the system from the maximum power. The lowest power loss is given by the aerodynamic drag power $P_D = v_a F_D$ where F_D is the aerodynamic drag force, see eq. 2.1 using C_D . From this eq. 2.2 results to be an upper bound on the useable power any flying device can extract from the wind field by replacing C_L with a more general resultant aerodynamic force coefficient C_R , also taking into account e.g. additional drag contributions like on-board turbines and neglecting cosine losses.

Figure 2.2: AWE power production concepts using lift mode (left) or drag mode (right) for crosswind power harvesting [16].

2.1.2 Concepts

As described in sect. 2.1.1, there are two modes for harvesting power with AWES in crosswind flight, see fig. 2.2:

- drag mode, propelling on-board turbines which add extra drag to the AWES
- lift mode, powering a ground-based generator using the tension on the tether.

Apart from crosswind flight, there are also other approaches to airborne power generation, see for example [14]. The flying devices can be categorised further discerning fixed-wing and soft kite structures, resembling aircraft and soft kite, respectively. There are multiple AWES in development by various companies, a few exemplary concepts are discussed below and shown in fig. 2.3, however many more combinations of the basic concepts are realised. In addition to electrical power generation AWES are also used for vehicle propulsion, which is not further discussed here. An overview of the current state of the industry can be found in [15].

Drag Mode - On-board Generation

When generating power on-board, a conducting tether is needed connecting the device to the ground transmitting generated electrical power to the consumer, which is also strong enough to withstand high crosswind tether tension. When transmitting the power both Ohmic losses and tether weight are lowest when using high voltage cables. Isolation of the conductor and on-board generators further increase both drag and mass of the AWES. Using the generator in motor mode, the on-board turbines can be used for safer vertical take-off and landing compared to horizontal take-off and landing of standard aircrafts. An on-board power generation fixed-wing kite concept was prominently realised by the Californian startup Makani [18] with e.g. kiteKRAFT [21] currently continuing development in this area.

Figure 2.3: Different AWES: showing SkySails [17], Makani [18], Kitepower [6], Ampyx Power [19] and EnerKite [20] (top left to bottom right) systems. Images from [16].

Lift Mode - Ground-based Generation

Using tether tension to unroll the tether from a ground-based drum and thus powering an electric generator does not require a conducting tether. It does however require control strategies for a cycle of flight operations (pumping cycle), where after the tether is unrolled to its maximum length it has to be reeled back in. While power is harvested during *reel-out* phase, it is consumed during *reel-in* phase. For reel-in the flight pattern is changed to one with strongly reduced lifting force, such that on average over a complete pumping cycle power is harvested. As mostly the lifting force of the wing in crosswind flight is used, this type of power production is referred to as *lift mode*. A more detailed explanation on the simulation of this flight pattern and resulting power production is given in sect. 2.1.4.

Many current AWES use lift mode power production combined with soft wing flying devices delivered by surf kite manufacturers, which are then controlled via the relative length of the steering lines. Some prototypes connect the main steering tethers directly to the ground station, for example EnerKite [20]. SkySails [17] and Kitepower [6] use kites controlled by an airborne kite control unit (KCU), which are connected to the ground station by a single tether, see fig. 2.3. Currently AWES are being launched by different companies: In early 2021 SkySails started its series production of an AWES [5] and also Kitepower is currently piloting their 100 kW system [22]

Lift mode power production is also realised using fixed-wing kite systems akin to sail planes, for example by Ampyx Power [19].

Flexible kite systems are generally much lighter than fixed-wing kite systems, are also easier to

Kite properties		Tether properties		Operational limits		Representative reel-out state	
projected area	19.75 m ²	density	724 kg m ⁻³	min reeling speed	2 m s ⁻¹	Azimuth angle	13 °
mass	22.8 kg	diameter	4 mm	max reeling speed	10 m s ⁻¹	course angle	100 °
$C_{L,\text{powered}}$	0.9	$C_{D,\text{tether}}$	1.1	min tether force	300 N		
$C_{D,\text{powered}}$	0.2			max tether force	5 000 N		
$C_{L,\text{depowered}}$	0.2						
$C_{D,\text{depowered}}$	0.1						

Table 2.1: System properties of the Kitepower V3 system used in the QSM power harvesting simulation. All properties are chosen to be the same as in [10].

steer and in case of a crash are less likely to pose danger of considerable damage. Rigid wing systems generally have a much higher lift-to-drag ratio, leading to faster crosswind flight motion and thus potential for significantly higher power output per wing area while making precise and safe controls even more important.

2.1.3 Kitepower V3 System

The prototype system used in this work is the 25 m² wing area Kitepower V3 with a ground station nominal power of 20 kW, see fig. 2.3, top right. A system including the Kitepower V3 was used to determine lift and drag coefficients for powered and depowered flight positions [23]. The used system components have been developed in the years leading up to 2012 by the kite power research group of Delft University of Technology, therefore the power results in this work are not representative for the current state of development in the AWE field but rather to be interpreted conceptually. Selection and implementation of the Kitepower V3 system follows [10], used system parameters are collected in tab. 2.1. The lift and drag coefficients of the powered and depowered kite are set to constants even though during real operation of kites, these parameters vary. The selection in [10] follows the findings by Oehler and Schmehl [23].

2.1.4 Traction Power Generation - Flight Simulation

AWE simulation models aim to provide resulting mechanical power for further conversion in the generator from input system parameters, see sect. 2.1.3, and wind conditions. The model as well as the AWE prototype in this work focus on traction power generation of a flying device tethered to the ground station. For the given conditions, it describes the operational parameters like tether length, tether force and elevation angle, ultimately resulting in a power output.

Dynamic Model

Dynamic models describe the dynamics of all major system components combined, namely the tether, the kite and the generator. The components are modelled to varying detail, for example using six degrees of freedom for the respective components in this recent work [8]. More approaches are discussed e.g. in [24] and [9], but will not be discussed in further detail in this work.

Dynamic models tend to require increasing computing power when considering more detailed dynamics of the kite, tether and complete system. They can also provide a way for validation of simplified models that do not require complicated flight control algorithms and means to test such

Figure 2.4: Idealised pumping cycle flight trajectory for the QSM. Crosswind flight motion is not resolved in the traction phase. [25]

control algorithms. Such simplifications can be used to estimate power production on a larger scale, especially looking at multiple locations for power maps.

Quasi-Steady Model

In this work the Quasi-Steady Model (QSM) described by Van der Vlugt et al. in [9] is used to simulate the AWES. The QSM describes the cyclic motion of the kite as a sequence of steady state changes, each at equilibrium of aerodynamic (\vec{F}_a), tether (\vec{F}_t) and gravitational (\vec{F}_g) forces, on a predefined flight path. This assumption can be made when the timescale of dynamic processes is short compared to the timescales of performed flight manoeuvres or complete pumping cycles, which holds for kites with large surface-to-mass ratio. The kite is represented by a geometrical point.

The flight is therefore only described by an individual set of analytic equations for every part of the pumping cycle: traction ($t_0 \rightarrow t_A$), retraction ($t_A \rightarrow t_B$) and transition phase ($t_B \rightarrow t_C$), see fig. 2.4.

The image shows the projection of the flight trajectory on the plane of direction (X_w) and height (Z_w) in the wind speed (v_w) reference frame. The elevation angle of the kite β is shown at the start of the pumping cycle (time t_0 , angle β_0) and for the depicted kite position. The device position in the air is given by the azimuth and elevation angle, the kite wind speed direction on the tangential plane is given by the course angle, the angle affected most by the steering system, see [9] for detailed description of the coordinate system. Settings used for these angles are given in tab. 2.1, the elevation angle is adapted to the wind conditions.

The model is not designed to accurately describe launch and landing situations, where the tether length and kite size are of similar dimensions leading to strong inertial force contributions in the force equilibrium. Following the different dimensions of tether length and kite size, the tether is assumed to be an inelastic and mostly straight connection to the point mass of the kite, where sagging due to gravitational loading is accounted for.

Kite properties typically vary during operation but are assumed to be constant throughout each phase. On the other hand, atmospheric properties, such as wind speed and density, are assumed to be constant over all simulated pumping cycles while varying with altitude. This input to the simulation,

referred to as *vertical wind profile*, is central to the analysis performed in this work.

Equilibrium State

The ansatz for the modelling of the force equilibrium states is discussed briefly, a more detailed explanation is found in the original paper [9].

The integral aerodynamic force on the system \vec{F}_a is given as the sum of lift (\vec{F}_L) and drag force (\vec{F}_D). While the lift force is only determined by the kite, the drag force is combined from kite and tether drag. Both are described in similar fashion to eq. 2.1. With the apparent wind velocity $\vec{v}_a = \vec{v}_w - \vec{v}_k$ at the kite with arbitrary velocity \vec{v}_k and wind speed \vec{v}_w the forces are given by

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{F}_a &= \vec{F}_L + \vec{F}_D \\ F_L &= \frac{1}{2}\rho S C_L v_a^2 \\ F_D &= \frac{1}{2}\rho S C_{D,k} v_a^2 + \frac{1}{8}\rho d_t r C_{D,c} v_a^2\end{aligned}\tag{2.3}$$

where C_L and $C_{D,k}$ are the aerodynamic lift and drag coefficients, respectively, and S the projected surface area of the kite. In [9], following previous work, one fourth of the tether drag force is incorporated into the kite drag, estimated as the drag of a cylinder with diameter d_t and length r in cross flow with drag coefficient $C_{D,c}$.

This aerodynamic force \vec{F}_a is set to equilibrium with the gravitational force of the kite \vec{F}_{g^*} and the tether force \vec{F}_t^* , see eq. 2.4. The starred versions of tether and gravitational force have the gravitational contribution of the tether removed or added, respectively.

$$\vec{F}_t^* + \vec{F}_{g^*} + \vec{F}_a = 0\tag{2.4}$$

This results in an expression for the lift-to-drag ratio F_L/F_D depending on the kinematic ratio $\kappa = v_{a,\tau}/v_{a,r}$ of the tangential and the radial apparent wind speeds, see eq. 2.5.

$$\frac{F_L}{F_D} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{F_a v_a}{\vec{F}_a \cdot \vec{v}_a}\right)^2 - 1}\tag{2.5}$$

For this equation the kinematic ratio is updated iteratively to find the best solution, where the result is sufficiently close to the given lift-to-drag ratio of the kite. This approach cannot produce any result for larger gravitational than aerodynamic force contribution in flight direction, as physically no quasi-steady equilibrium state is reachable. This leads to cut-in and cut-out situations, where the system cannot operate anymore according to the QSM. Other situations also lead to cut-out of the system, e.g. too low or too high tether tension. Thus the QSM is limited e.g. by the maximum tether force and the maximum reeling speed of the used system, given in tab. 2.1.

Pumping Cycle

The different phases of a pumping cycle, see fig. 2.4 pose different problem parameters to the model in eq. 2.5. Transition between phases is achieved mostly by changing model parameters, foremost by setting different aerodynamic coefficients of the kite in the lift and drag force calculation. In reality this is achieved by controlled flight maneuvers, such as reducing the angle of attack of the kite in order to retract the kite back to minimum tether length at minimal cost of energy. During this so-called

Figure 2.5: QSM tether force modelling compared real flight data, showing the tether force at the ground end of the tether over a full pumping cycle [9].

retraction phase, the force is kept constant in order to minimize retraction time and thus maximised power output is expected.

In order to start power harvesting again, the large elevation angle reached at the end of the retraction phase has to be reduced and on the other hand the tether force has to be increased. This task is performed by the *transition phase*. Here the aerodynamic coefficients are set to their traction values, the kite is powered, but flown in a downward direction, keeping the tether reeling speed at zero as long as the tether force is within its bounds. When the required starting position to start traction is reached, meaning elevation angle and consequently tether force, the transition phase is completed.

At this point the *traction phase* is initiated, where power is harvested via crosswind motion until the tether reaches its maximum length. Flight patterns of the crosswind motion, such as circles or figures of eight, are not resolved in this model but represented by a time average traction force and consequently average power. This approach is tested on experimental data [9] and can be further validated using dynamic models and more experimental data.

After reaching the maximum tether length, the pumping cycle begins anew with the retraction phase.

At time t the power $P(t)$ is given by the tether force and its reeling speed $P(t) = F_t(t)v_t(t)$ yielding a time averaged power \bar{P}_i for phase i . The mean cycle power results from the average traction power and time duration Δt_i of each phase to be

$$P_m = \frac{\sum_i \bar{P}_i \Delta t_i}{\sum_i \Delta t_i},$$

giving the available mechanical power after completing the pumping cycle once.

The QSM was validated against real flight data for both moderate and strong winds at Rotterdam Harbour in The Netherlands using a 20 kW system [9]. Good agreement is observed when including gravitational effects into the QSM, as shown for the tether force at the ground station in fig. 2.5.

The QSM settings used in this work follow [10].

SLSQP Optimization

Optimal parameters for the QSM are found via minimizing an objective function using sequential least squares optimization (SLSQP), a method to solve differentiable constrained non-linear problems.

The objective function is defined via the negative of the power output, such that a minimum in the objective function implies maximal harvesting power. Additionally the optimization is constrained via equality and inequality constraint functions, which are evaluated similarly to the objective function, and either leading to required or forbidden parts of the parameter space of the optimization.

The SLSQP algorithm as described by Dieter Kraft in [26] uses a quasi-Newton method on the Lagrange function, defined by the objective function, equality and inequality constraints. Its implementation in pyOptSparse by MDO Lab is used in this work [27], previously described in pyOpt [28].

2.1.5 Economic Evaluation

When evaluating the potential of airborne wind energy, the estimated power production has to be considered in an economic setting, as done for example in [29]. As the prices at the power market are updated more than daily, good time resolution of the resulting estimated power is required for a detailed economic comparison between energy sources. In this work, the focus lies more on comparing multiple locations and thus averaged metrics are chosen.

When comparing on a yearly averaged basis, the estimated harvesting power at a location is given in terms of annual energy production (AEP) calculated as produced energy minus the consumed energy of a year, given in [MWh/a]. The energy balance is represented by the average power, and thus in a given timespan is obtained by multiplication of its average power with the timespan.

Another important quantity when evaluating the economic potential of AWE, and especially when comparing to wind turbines, is the capacity factor (c_f in [%]). It describes the energy generated by a system, divided by the maximum amount of energy that could have been generated by said system when operating continuously at *nominal power* during a specific time period, defaulting to one year. The nominal power P_n of a system is defined as the maximum average cycle power, meaning the maximum of the power curve of the system. Further descriptions of the metrics can be found in [30].

2.2 Wind data

As AWES can harvest power at variable altitudes, estimating harvesting power requires vertical wind profiles, meaning wind data for a range of heights.

2.2.1 Atmospheric Boundary Layer

The atmosphere consists of multiple layers of which the lowest is the atmospheric boundary layer. Here the atmospheric behaviour is influenced mostly by contact with the planetary surface, its resulting drag, and correspondingly the changing surface radiation over the turn of a day [31]. Above, the atmosphere is described as free atmosphere, where the wind is approximately parallel to the isobars, independent of surface conditions. More detailed discussion of the atmospheric layers, their daily evolution and wind conditions is found in [7].

With tether lengths of typically around 200 m in this work, and up to ≈ 500 m for different systems, AWES fly in the region of the atmospheric boundary layer.

The vertical wind profiles for estimating the power production of current AWES can thus be approximated using the logarithmic wind law, which holds up to about 500 m altitude in the atmospheric boundary layer. The wind speed v_w at altitude z is given as

$$v_w(z) = v_{w,ref} \frac{\ln(z/z_0)}{\ln(z_{ref}/z_0)},$$

where $v_{w,ref}$ is a reference wind speed at reference altitude z_{ref} . z_0 is the aerodynamic roughness length [32].

Similarly, the decreasing air density ρ with increasing altitude is approximately given by the barometric altitude formula

$$\rho(z) = \rho_0 \exp\left(-\frac{z}{H_\rho}\right), \quad (2.6)$$

with $\rho_0 = 1.225 \text{ kg/m}^3$ giving the standard atmospheric density at sea level at standard temperature of $T_0 = 15^\circ\text{C}$ and $H_\rho = 8.55 \text{ km}$ as scale height for density [32].

The logarithmic wind law quite accurately describes the neutral atmospheric boundary layer, meaning overcast and windy conditions, while other weather situations are modeled far less accurately and more singular events such as low level jets cannot be accounted for [10].

For creating detailed maps of AWE power, at optimum measured real wind profiles for many timepoints from different locations are measured and used in the flight simulation to obtain their respective power. As this cannot be realised, an approach is using the ERA5 Reanalysis data [1].

2.2.2 ERA5 Reanalysis Data

ERA5 [1] combines historical observations and observations up to current time, with a delay of at most 3 months, into global estimates of a large number of atmospheric, land and oceanic climate variables using advanced modelling and data assimilation systems. The data covers the Earth on a about 30 km grid and resolves the atmosphere using 137 model levels from the surface up to a height of about 80 km [33]: The lower model levels refer to the higher altitudes and vice versa. Model level 137 gives data for an altitude of 10 m from the surface, thus the highest model levels are shaped according to local surface elevation [34]. The definition of ERA5 model levels and coefficients used for conversion to different height measures is given in [35]. Advanced information on ERA5 in general and the reanalysis method can be in the documentation [36].

Data Variables and Resolution

For this thesis, the chosen ERA5 data spans the full European map (latitudes [65,30], longitudes [-20, 20]) at a grid resolution of .25 degrees latitude and longitude, for a timespan of 11 years, from 01.01.2010 until 31.12.2020 with hourly resolution. One sample in the dataset corresponds to the the ensemble of one hour averages of all available data parameters at one specific time and location.

ERA5 horizontal wind speed in northern (v [m/s]) and eastern direction (u [m/s]), surface pressure (p_0 [Pa]), temperature (T [K]) and specific humidity (q [kg/kg]) is obtained for a range of model

levels [137,112] for each sample at a specific location and time [37]. The surface geopotential is also obtained, which is later used to determine a coarse topographical map for orientation.

Height Calculation

When simulating the flight of an AWES system, the height that is relevant to the system is the height it has above ground, corresponding to h_l of the wind speed data for model level l . The model levels are counted upwards in this case, for convenience. Measuring the altitude in model levels does however not directly correspond to such an altitude.

However, the geopotential Φ_l can be determined for a model level l using the temperature and specific humidity and the geopotential at the surface Φ_s [34]. The calculation adds up the geopotential contribution of each model level step Δ_i until the desired level l is reached, such that

$$\Phi_l = \Phi_s + \sum_{i=1}^l \Delta_i.$$

The geopotential height results from dividing the geopotential by Earth's standard gravitational acceleration, which has a fixed value of $g = 9.80665 \text{ m/s}^2$, and is measured in meters above the mean sea level in ERA5 [34]. By subtracting the geopotential height at the surface h_s^Φ from the geopotential height of the chosen model level h_l^Φ resulting, the height above ground h_l can thus be obtained. Therefore when calculating the geopotential and its corresponding height starting with $\Phi_s = 0$, the height above ground is obtained,

$$\begin{aligned} h_l &= h_l^\Phi - h_s^\Phi \\ &= (\Phi_s + \sum_{i=1}^l \Delta_i)/g - \Phi_s/g \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^l \Delta_i/g. \end{aligned}$$

This way of height calculation from [34] was implemented to improve the ERA5 wind potential analysis [7] in [38] and is kept conceptually the same in this work as it was then, with slight modifications.

From this approach also the air density ρ at a given level can be obtained, using the temperature T and full level pressure $p_f = (p_l + p_{(l+1)})/2$ of a given model level l and time point via

$$\rho = \frac{p_f}{R_d \cdot T}, \quad (2.7)$$

with the gas constant $R_d = 287.06 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ kg}^{-1}$.

A vertical wind profile for AWES simulations is determined by linearly interpolating the model level heights and corresponding wind speed data to the requested height range steps. In this work the wind speeds are determined at [10., 50., 100., 140., 180., 220., 260., 300., 340., 380., 420., 500., 600.] meters altitude above ground. This differs from the selection in previous work on clustering wind profiles [10] in order to match the ERA5 model level height steps as well as typical flight altitudes of

200 m to 400 m.

ERA5 Uncertainty

The ERA5 dataset includes information on the model based uncertainty of the parameters, which is rather intended as a measure to identify more/less accurate regions in time and space within ERA5 than giving a measure for real absolute errors of the data [39]. The production process and known resulting strengths and issues are in detail discussed in [40].

A comparison to measured wind data at six tall towers at heterogeneous locations in [41] gives an overview of the real absolute errors to be expected when using ERA5 data. There errors range from 1% to 7% at offshore and flat, sea-level sites, respectively. Limited spatial resolution leads to larger errors at mountainous and forested sites, with strong impact of varying land use and topography. Thus also coastal locations are to be considered with caution, giving about 14% error in wind speed in [41]. Earlier studies comparing ERA5 to previous modelling frameworks show overall good performance for ERA5 [42], but find it to underestimate wind speeds especially in mountainous areas and propose to use ERA5 with local wind-speed corrections [43].

2.2.3 Resource Analysis

The ERA5 wind data on a 1x1 degree grid was used in [7] to assess the wind resource potential for AWE in Europe, using a height calculation based on additional geopotential information and fixed model level heights. A hypothetical situation is assessed where an AWES always operates at optimal height, determined via maximal wind speed, ranging between 50 m and 500 m altitude. The resulting resource potential is compared to a 100 m fixed height scenario, representing the hub height of a wind turbine. This comparison stresses the opportunity of AWES to continuously adjust harvesting height as well as accessing higher altitudes than conventional wind turbines. The scenarios are compared among other aspects with respect to wind speed, wind power density and power availability.

The resource analysis finds significant increase in resource potential using AWES compared to 100 m hub height turbines, especially over the land mass and coastal areas of Europe, showing an increase in the wind power density which is available for 95% of the time by a factor of two.

Wind Power Density

The wind power density P_w is used as a measure for wind resource potential, and is determined from the wind speed v_w and air density ρ at a given altitude via

$$P_w = \frac{1}{2} \rho v_w^3. \quad (2.8)$$

In [7] the air density is approximated using the barometric formula given in Eq.2.6.

Percentiles

The shape of a probability distribution is characterised via its percentiles. Inspecting at a given location an ensemble of time points each resulting in a power density results in such a probability distribution. Its 5th percentile then gives information about baseload power, as for 95% of the time

the power exceeds the 5th percentile value, while the 50th percentile represents the median of the distribution.

Since in general energy conversion processes are limited both by lower and upper bounds, for example cut-in and cut-out wind speeds, the distribution shapes play a large role when determining the resulting energies. Therefore the 5th, 32nd and 50th percentiles of the distributions are given in the resource analysis [7].

Availability

Taking the opposite approach to percentiles, also the availability A of a given power density can be determined via its percentile rank PR

$$A = 100\% - PR,$$

such that an availability of e.g. 80% for a power density of 40 W m^{-2} implies that for 80% of the time the power density is at least 40 W m^{-2} [7].

Betz limit and Power Harvesting Factor

The power harvesting performance of a system can be evaluated when comparing the harvested power P per projected wing surface area to the wind power density available in the air mass P_w from eq. 2.8. The resulting ratio, called power harvesting factor ζ is limited to the Betz limit of maximal $16/27$, almost reached by recent wind turbines. Not all available power in the wind can be harvested as a direct consequence of the continuity equation [12].

2.3 Wind Profile Clustering

Evaluating vertical wind profile data with a high temporal and spatial resolution quickly turns into large datasets, which can be parametrised using the wind profile clustering algorithm proposed in [10]. A set of representative vertical wind profiles, so called *cluster profiles*, is defined and each sample is matched to one of these cluster profiles. The absolute wind speed scale of the cluster profiles is not relevant, rather the wind speed at a given reference height is set and the rest of the profile is scaled accordingly.

The clustering procedure first includes preprocessing steps to normalise the wind speed data as well as using a principal component analysis to reduce the dimensionality of the dataset focusing on the variance of the wind profiles. Then the preprocessed and parametrised profiles are clustered using the k-means clustering algorithm, defining the resulting cluster centers as representative cluster profiles.

Performing the clustering procedure on large wind datasets can yield representative wind profiles, which could in turn be used to compare performance of different AWESs.

2.3.1 Principal Component Analysis

The principal component analysis (PCA) effectively reduces the dimensionality of the data while preserving meaningful properties such as the variance of the original data, reducing further computing

time. This emphasis on more important structures can also be beneficial for classification such as the k-means clustering algorithm.

In more detail, a PCA determines a transformation from the original coordinate system to the principal component (PC) coordinate system. For a vertical wind profile this corresponds to changing from giving the wind speed at each height step to superimposing multipliers of PC contributions onto the mean vertical wind profile of the dataset. Thus each PC is represented by a vertical wind profile and contributes in the superposition depending on its coefficient. The PC coefficients are therefore the new representation of the original vertical wind profile and the individual PC profiles are given by unit vectors on their respective new coordinate axes, starting at the origin of the PC coordinate system, which is given by the mean vertical wind profile of the dataset [10].

The PCs are determined and ordered such that the first PCs account for most of the variance in the dataset, therefore choosing only the first 5 components was enough to account for more than 90% of the variance in the dataset in [10].

Concept and Implementation

The implementation of a PCA is illustrated for a dataset X containing columns of wind speeds for n_f different heights measured n times, corresponding to the n_f features that the PCA is supposed to describe. The PCA tries to find linear combinations \vec{a} of the respective feature columns to define new coordinate axes in this multidimensional space that best describe the data. Meaning that the data shows little variation orthogonally from these axes while along the axes the data shows maximal variance. This process can be translated to solving the eigenvector \vec{a} and eigenvalue λ problem for maximal variance in the dataset as $var(X\vec{a}) = \vec{a}^T C \vec{a} = \lambda$ with the covariance matrix of the dataset C [44].

The applied linear combinations $X\vec{a}$ for each eigenvector correspond to the principal components of the dataset, sorted by maximal eigenvalue. Looking at the eigenvectors \vec{a} gives insight to the wind profile shapes represented by the respective principal component.

Using more principal components to describe a dataset contributes to the amount of variability that is retained up to summing up all variances of all principal components giving the total dataset variance. Thus a standard measure for the quality of a chosen set of principal components is the proportion of the total variance. Commonly at least 70% are required for an adequate description, however strongly depending on the field of application [44].

Finding principal components of centered variables does not impact the solution apart from centering, but transports the PCA to a singular value decomposition problem of the centered dataset matrix. This approach decomposes any arbitrary matrix into the product of an orthonormal with a diagonal and another transposed orthonormal matrix, matching the dimensions of the original matrix. From this decomposition, the linear combination vectors \vec{a} are obtained [44].

In this work the sklearn implementation for PCA [45] is used, of which the detailed PCA procedure is explained in [46]. This implementation uses singular value decomposition in combination with the probabilistic approach by N. Halko [47] for large datasets.

2.3.2 k-means Clustering

In order to identify representative wind profile shapes of the wind resource, k-means clustering [48] is used on the wind resource represented in principal component space, using the implementation from

[10]. To obtain real vertical wind profile shapes, the clustering results are thus back-transformed from principal component to physical space.

The respective centroid of a cluster is chosen as representative vertical wind profile shape for all samples in the wind resource matched to the specific cluster. Vice versa, the clusters are chosen iteratively such that the sum of the squared Euclidean distances to the respective matched centroids over all samples are minimised.

Increasing the number of clusters for representing a dataset decreases the squared Euclidean distances, also referred to as within-cluster sum of squares (WCSS), thus choosing a number of clusters where the WCSS is strongly decreased is preferred. Another option is to investigate the similarity of a sample to other samples in its matched cluster relative to the similarity to the nearest neighbouring cluster's matched samples. Referred to elbow and silhouette method, respectively, these methods were used in [10] to determine a useful number of clusters for single locations and up to 45 locations in the Netherlands. It was found that the silhouette score decreases with the number of clusters, which is interpreted as promoting a small number of clusters to maintain cluster cohesiveness.

Another important performance measure for the clustering algorithm is comparison to the original dataset, where using the centroid vertical wind profile shapes, the cluster representation of the wind resource dataset is obtained. During preprocessing each sample is normalised by division with its respective 90th percentile of the absolute wind speed [10], the back-transformed clustering results thus represent the sample wind profile only after being multiplied with its respective norm factor.

In this work, the cluster profiles are always investigated when scaled such that the wind speed at reference height is 1 rather than its original clustering wind speed $v_{w,100m,c}$. The cluster wind speed at reference height is then scaled to a range of $v_{w,100m}$ when e.g. determining a power curve for the cluster using the QSM. Therefore when comparing to an original sample the backscaling comprises the sample denormalisation multiplied by the clustering wind speed $v_{w,100m,c}$, and can thus be directly compared to e.g. the power curve wind speeds.

In conclusion, for any sample the respective cluster representation is defined by the matched cluster and the backscaling wind speed. The reference height is set to 100 m, as set in [10].

The two representations can then be compared simply by finding the differences in wind speed at each height step. In [10] the accuracy of the clustering representation with respect to absolute wind speeds is compared to a representation fitting logarithmic vertical wind profiles to the sample wind profiles, and is overall found to outperform the logarithmic profiles in case of more than 3 clusters. The height dependence of the accuracy is also an important aspect considered in [10]. Following this analysis, 8 clusters were chosen to represent the wind resource in [10], as a trade-off between the performance indicators and with the aim to provide in depth and meaningful interpretation of the resulting clusters.

Concept and Implementation

The k-means clustering [48] as implemented in sklearn [49, 50] is a widely used clustering algorithm, trying to separate the samples in k disjoint groups of equal variance. The mean values of the respective clusters are called the cluster centroids, and are iteratively chosen to minimize the within-cluster-sum-of-squares criterion, meaning the sum of the resulting squared Euclidean distances to the matched samples. The iterative algorithm is described by the following steps [48]:

1. Choose k random cluster centroids, e.g. from the samples.

2. Match each sample to the centroid at closest Euclidean distance.
3. Replace each of the k centroids with the mean formed by all matched samples.
4. Repeat steps 2 and 3 until a stable configuration is reached.

The k-means clustering algorithm is very robust in finding a solution, it however performs poorly on elongated or very irregular cluster shapes. This is caused by the algorithms tendency to rather produce spherical clusters with equal radius and sample size. As the principal components already parametrise the cluster shapes, especially irregular or elongated shapes are not commonly expected. Especially for more difficult datasets, the results depend very strongly on the initialization of the centroids [50].

ERA5 Wind Resource Analysis

The wind resource potential evaluation by Bechtle et al. [7] is updated with a more precise altitude calculation as well as higher map resolution and larger evaluated timespan. Focus is laid on the resulting updated results in comparison to the previous findings.

3.1 Resource Analysis Concept

The European wind resource potential for AWE was evaluated by Bechtle et al. in [7] based on the ERA5 wind data [1], showing strong potential for AWES compared to the wind resource at 100 m. AWE harvesting is represented by choosing the maximal wind speed in the height range between 50 m and 500 m. The resource analysis is described in sec. 2.2.3, most important improvements in this work are the variable model level height calculation and an increased resolution of 0.25° compared to 1° in [7]. In addition, instead of a time range from years 2011 to 2017, now the years 2010 to 2020 are used in the evaluation. The wind data processing is updated to use xarray [51] and netCDF4 [52]. The impact of the introduced changes on the resulting resource evaluation compared to the findings in [7] is discussed in this section. The observation of overall strong wind resource potential for AWES is confirmed, with even stronger increase with respect to conventional wind turbines, represented by the 100 m reference case.

3.2 European Wind Resource

The wind resource is evaluated with respect to wind speeds and power densities. Detailed information on the processing and evaluation for the different maps can be found in [7]. The evaluation only considers wind resource potential, therefore technical, operational and harvesting efficiency considerations have to be kept in mind when interpreting the following results for AWES. In addition, more extreme values of possible power harvesting increase for AWES are observed in mountainous regions, where the uncertainty of the used ERA5 wind data is a lot higher than on flat topographies, see sec. 2.2.2.

The wind resource is displayed mostly via its percentiles, as they give insight into the most important features of the resource: The 5th percentile gives information on minimal conditions present most of the time, which can give insight into whether specific baseload requirements are fulfilled. Similarly, the 32nd percentile described minimal conditions present at about $2/3$ of the time. The 50th percentile

Figure 3.1: The wind resource for a typical conventional wind turbine with 100 m hub height is evaluated. The wind speed distribution is characterised via its 5th, 32nd, and 50th percentiles.

gives the median of the distribution, see sec.2.2.3.

3.2.1 Resource at 100m

The wind speed and wind power density distributions for 100 m, representing the standard wind turbine hub height, is overall very similar to the results found in [7]. The improved resolution leads to a slightly higher range of e.g. wind speeds, as higher wind speed contributions are more likely to be resolved instead of averaged out. The improved resolution is also clearly visible in the contour lines following the coast even more precisely, see e.g. fig. 3.1 the 9 m s^{-1} line between Great Britain and France.

The wind speeds are very similar over the open sea but show visible decrease over the landmass compared to the results in [7], which is attributed to the improved height calculation. Height calculation is not expected to show strong impact on open sea results, as there is no significant surface elevation to be considered in either height calculation approach.

The wind power density shows the same similarities and differences, in a more pronounced way, as the power density is proportional to the cubed wind speed, see fig. 3.2.

3.2.2 Optimal AWE Resource

The wind resource available for an AWE flying at optimal height between 50 m and 500 m is shown in fig. 3.3 and fig. 3.4 for wind speed and wind power density, respectively.

The wind speed resources for AWE are very similar to what is found in [7], observing lower wind speeds mainly in mountainous regions. The decreased wind speeds over land mass for the 100 m turbine case, see sec. 3.2.1 lead to much more pronounced increase for AWE operation versus wind turbines than found in [7]. The increase factors for the power density in fig. 3.4 now range up to 10 or even 20 for the 5th percentile, while in [7] less pronounced increase factors of at maximum 3.5 are found. Therefore, the potential for AWE is found to be even more striking, however it has to be considered that not all of the available wind power is harvested but a fraction depending on the used

Figure 3.2: The wind resource for a typical conventional wind turbine with 100 m hub height is evaluated. The wind power density distribution is characterised via its 5th, 32nd, and 50th percentiles.

harvesting system. This fraction is also smaller for AWESs than for conventional wind turbines, see sec. 2.2.3.

Figure 3.3: The wind resource for AWES always operating at optimal height with maximal wind speed, within 50 m and 500 m is evaluated. The wind speed distribution is characterised via its 5th, 32nd, and 50th percentiles (upper). The increase factor with respect to the 100 m reference case for each percentile distribution is also included (lower).

Figure 3.4: The wind resource for AWES always operating at optimal height with maximal wind speed, within 50 m and 500 m is evaluated. The wind speed distribution is characterised via its 5th, 32nd, and 50th percentiles (upper). The increase factor with respect to the 100 m reference case for each percentile distribution is also included (lower).

3.2.3 Integrated Power Density

The analysis for integrated power density in [7] was aimed to show harvesting potential for very high altitudes and thus accessing strong high altitude winds. In this work the focus is laid on current AWESs, mostly operating at heights up to 500 m. Still, the interpretation remains valid that there is a large pool of wind energy available when exploiting high altitude winds, see fig. 3.5 in the center frame. Comparing the integrated power density for AWES (center) and turbine height ranges (left) as shown in fig. 3.5 in the right frame, the increase ratio between the two cases is at least 4, up to 28 favouring AWES harvesting especially over the land mass.

3.2.4 Availability

The power availability for 40, 300, and 1 600 W m^{-2} of the wind resource gives insight into baseload support potential, continuous moderate and peak harvesting potential, respectively. It is compared for the optimally operating AWES compared and the 100 m reference case in fig. 3.6. Similar distributions with overall higher availability are observed, compared to the findings in [7]. The availability more strongly discerns land mass and open sea regions than [7], which is again attributed to the higher resolution. Due to the higher resolution, the availability also reaches much lower values than before, for resolved locations with very low wind speeds.

Availability of 40 W m^{-2} for different operational height ranges of AWESs are displayed in fig. 3.7 relative to the 50 m and 500 m AWES case considered so far. Due to the introduced height calculation

Figure 3.5: Wind resource power density integrated over height for a typical height range of conventional wind turbines (left), the wind resource available for current AWES (center), and the respective increase ratio (right). This shows the integrated potential for AWES.

only a maximum height of 1 250 m is available for all data points within the used model level height range, while in [7] a maximum height of 1 500 m was considered. Compared to the findings in [7] mostly the mountainous regions show lowest availability, which is in part compensated when reaching up to higher altitudes. As the 50 m and 500 m AWES case already shows maximal availability over large regions, most increase is observed at mountainous regions again. Here using higher altitude AWES is strongly favoured, when considering the resource potential only.

Figure 3.6: Availability of 40, 300, and 1600 W m⁻² wind power density for AWES always operating at optimal height with maximal wind speed, within 50 m and 500 m (upper), and its relative increase with respect to the 100 m height case (lower).

Figure 3.7: Availability of 40 W m^{-2} wind power density for optimal height AWES cases with 300, 1000, and 1250 m ceiling (upper) and the corresponding decrease or increase relative to the optimal height AWES case within 50 m and 500 m (lower).

Wind Resource Representation

The wind resource for AWE systems is described as a collection of vertical wind profiles at various time and space points. The procedure and resulting representation are discussed in detail, with a focus on regional distinction of the found representation. After defining the wind resource representation, its accuracy is validated against the original ERA5 wind data.

4.1 Concept

Assessing the resource with respect to AWE requires estimating AWES power harvesting via simulation on each individual vertical wind profile. This easily amounts up to immense computational requirements, especially when evaluating large timespans on large geographical regions, and when optimal cycle settings are identified each time. In this work 11 years of hourly data on an European map is evaluated, see sec. 2.2.2, amounting to 96,000 time samples for each of the about 23,000 locations. Using the wind resource representation algorithm, combining a principal component analysis and k-means clustering, as described in [10], makes it possible to simulate AWES power harvesting on the representation only, and then provides the opportunity to infer harvesting results for each location and time point.

Simulating the power harvesting characteristics on a vertical wind profile representing an hourly averaged wind speed does not consider the absolute wind direction in its northern and eastern components but could be impacted by the wind veer between different altitudes. Therefore the representation is aimed at describing the shapes of vertical wind profiles, independent of absolute wind directions and wind speeds, and the resulting representations are later scaled back to reconstruct the original sample.

A subset of the full original data is used to find the wind resource representation in form of cluster centroid vertical wind profiles, therefore called the training dataset. The so-found resource representation is then archived as a pipeline, such that any additional vertical wind profile can still be matched to its cluster vertical wind profile. In this way, the pipeline is once applied on the complete dataset determining the wind resource representation of the complete temporal and spatial extent of the data. Even though 80 clusters are chosen for the representation, many results are shown for 8 clusters to make the content more readable, the 80 cluster results are always included in the appendix.

Figure 4.1: Visual orientation showing the subset of 5000 training locations in (a) and the 1000 different locations used for validation in (b). Locations marked in red refer to more in detail evaluated single locations.

4.1.1 Training Data

The wind resource parametrisation is determined for the wind data from a subset of 5,000 of all locations, which were uniformly randomly selected from all possible locations in the European ERA5 wind data. The resulting map of training locations is shown in fig. 4.1(a).

Further consideration of the uniformly random selection of the training locations made it apparent that the open sea is overrepresented in such a selection. Due to the distortion of the map, the northern regions, mostly open sea, are overrepresented. Additionally, while the wind resource over land is highly diverse, open sea wind profiles are much more uniform with respect to each other. This difference is caused by the impact of the different surface elevations interacting with the wind resource. Thus the less diverse regions are overly represented in the training samples. Adapted choices for training locations could therefore improve precision over the land mass.

4.1.2 Preprocessing

Before applying the PCA and consequently the k-means clustering algorithm, the vertical wind profiles from ERA5 are subjected to a preprocessing procedure.

1. Only samples with a mean wind speed over all altitudes above 5 m s^{-1} are used in the training data.
2. The eastern and northern wind speed direction components are projected onto each sample's wind direction at 100 m reference height, resulting in parallel and perpendicular components.

3. The sample vertical wind profiles are normalised by division with the 90th percentile of the wind speed over all altitudes, the norm factor η .

This procedure focuses the vertical wind profile shape, meaning the relationships between different altitudes, over absolute wind speed and direction. Normalisation leads to a more compact wind resource representation, while also sometimes producing irregular wind profile shapes for low winds, as found in [10]. Therefore low wind samples are not included in the training data, but are predicted nevertheless using the defined representation. This cut also focuses the relevant wind speeds for AWES, which usually do not operate with wind speeds this low. Including such samples in the training therefore mostly deteriorates the prediction power of the representation in more relevant wind speed ranges, while not contributing significantly to an AWES power harvesting estimation. Effects of this procedure are evaluated when validating the parametrisation, see sec. 4.3.8.

4.1.3 Principal Component Analysis

The resulting preprocessed wind profile shapes are used to determine their principal components (PCs) as described in sec. 2.3.1. Using the first 5 PCs is found to describe the original data very accurately, increasing the number of PCs did not improve the representation as the resulting error was strongly dominated by the number of clusters.

PC Wind Profile Shapes

The unit vectors for each of the coordinate axes in PC space can be interpreted as respective PC wind profile shapes, while the origin of the PC coordinate space is placed at the mean vertical wind profile of all training samples, see fig. 4.2.

The sample mean profile in fig. 4.2(a) shows height dependence similar to the standard logarithmic profile expected in the boundary layer of the atmosphere.

The first and second PC shapes found in figs. 4.2(b), (c) match the PCs identified in [10], therefore the interpretation remains that the first PC accounts for strong perpendicular contributions, indicating that PC1 mostly characterises wind veer. While the second PC shows stronger change in parallel wind components, and thus wind shear.

Most PCs show largest contributions at the upper and lower ends of the height range, showing that in accordance with [10] most variance in the dataset is found at these heights. The fourth and fifth PCs in figs. 4.2(e), (f) show bulges in the center of the height range, they thus account for the remaining variance there.

Comparing the PC shapes for different training location setups overall shows no significant change in the profiles, which is seen as a hint that the principal components are a well-placed preparation to extract most significant traits.

The PC representation is reconstructed to the normal vertical wind profile coordinate system by superimposing the PC profile contributions onto the mean profile, as shown exemplary for the first and second PCs in fig. 4.3. There the contributions are weighted by their respective standard deviation, indicating the range of their contribution to the representation.

Figure 4.2: PC coordinate system origin and corresponding PC axis unit vector profile shapes for the 5 first PCs.

PC Space Parametrisation & Reconstruction

The resulting PC description and reconstruction of an exemplary sample on 5th March 2013, 6am at (lat 52.0, lon 5.0) close to the met mast Cabauw (Netherlands) is visualised in fig.4.4. The image shows the normalised original vertical wind profile in the top left frame. To its right the PC contributions are superimposed on the mean vertical wind profile with their respective contributions. In the bottom right frame all 5 selected PCs contribute, and no real difference to the original profile is visual. Both first and last frames include the reconstructed cluster profile (dashdotted, lower opacity) and its label number, which is discussed in sec. 4.1.4, to provide good visual reference for comparing both original and PC representation.

Figure 4.3: PC space contribution of the first and second PCs weighted with their respective standard deviation as multipliers, subtracted for [1] and [3] and added for [2] and [4].

4.1.4 Wind Profile Clustering

Using the PC space parametrisation of the training data, k-means clustering, see sec. 2.3.2, is used to identify inherent, possibly representative, vertical wind profiles of the data.

Concept: PC 1 & 2 Projection

In PC space, the vertical wind profiles of the individual samples are represented by one coordinate point, illustrated in fig. 4.5(a), projected onto only the first two PCs. Even though restricted to only two of 5 dimensions, visually already two potential cluster regions can be identified around $(-0.5, 0)$ and close to $(0.5, 0.5)$. This observation conceptually matches combining the offshore and onshore results in [10].

The clustering algorithm finds closest Euclidean distance clusters in the full PC space, again a projection onto the first two PCs and associated clusters is shown in fig. 4.5(b) for 8 clusters. The cluster matching shows some similarity to [10] especially for the first two clusters, however here comparison becomes increasingly difficult due to the different samples and locations used for training. The results for 80 clusters are included in A.1.

Figure 4.4: PC space reconstruction of an exemplary sample profile, starting at the mean [1] and superimposing the PC contributions of up to 5 PCs [6]. Including the 80 cluster reconstruction in the original and PC reconstruction for visual comparability (dashdotted, lower opacity). The matched cluster is indicated in the lower left corner of the sample profile frame. The exemplary sample refers to the wind data on 5th March 2013, 6am at (lat 52.0, lon 5.0) close to the met mast Cabauw (Netherlands).

Figure 4.5: Exemplary first and second PC space frequency projection of training on the 5 reference locations and the resulting cluster identification for 8 clusters.

Cluster Wind Profile Shapes

The cluster centroids of each cluster in PC space from fig. 4.5(b) can be transformed back to physical space such that each cluster is represented by its centroid's vertical wind profile.

Cluster Shape Scaling & Reconstruction

The resulting vertical wind profile of each cluster centroid is scaled such that the wind speed at the reference height of 100 m equals to $v_{w,100m} = 1 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. Therefore, when comparing to an original sample this scaling as well as the normalisation factor of the sample have to be taken into account, resulting in a backscaling factor for each sample.

When scaling the cluster profile to different $v_{w,100m}$ e.g. for power harvesting simulation at different absolute wind speeds, the scaled $v_{w,100m}$ can be directly matched to the backscaling of a sample to infer the power harvesting for said sample. This evidently also requires the sample to be matched to that specific cluster.

Using 8 Clusters

The wind profile shapes found for 8 clusters are shown in fig. 4.6. The first two profiles match the findings in [10] for the offshore datasets, showing mostly standard logarithmic and very uniform shapes. Also in accordance with [10], most deviation from standard logarithmic behaviour can be observed in the height regions above about 100 m. Both show little wind veer and shear, as seen in a well-mixed convective profile [10]. With increasing cluster number, more dominant wind shear and subsequently wind veer are observed. Logarithmic profile description gets less accurate, observing low-level jet behaviour in cluster 6, meaning higher wind speeds at lower altitude and lower wind speeds at higher altitude. In summary similar results to [10] are observed, however less jet-like profiles are found. Offshore locations could lead to low-level jets being more prominent in the training data than using more comprehensive training data, as done in this work.

Conformity to logarithmic profiles is interpreted visually, checking the monotonous increase in wind speed with height. This visual interpretation would best be supported by including a fit to a logarithmic profile for each cluster profile, as done in [10], from where conclusions on conformity and non-conformity are extrapolated for this work.

Training these 8 clusters on a different number of uniformly selected training locations does not show significant change above at maximum 200 training locations, which leads to the conclusion that the identified clusters represent core properties of the European wind resource.

For completeness the scale factors used to normalise the 100 m wind speed of each cluster shape are given by [1.065, 1.259, 1.193, 1.715, 1.651, 1.11, 1.514, 1.375], respectively.

Using 80 Clusters

In order to accurately describe the wind resource, 8 clusters do not suffice. Using 80 clusters gives a much more accurate description of the individual samples, see sec. 4.3. The resulting cluster profiles are included, see appendix A.1.2. The 80 different cluster shapes overall show similar properties as the 8 cluster profiles, but with more variation of wind veer and wind shear. Also many more low-level jet shapes are identified.

Figure 4.6: Resulting cluster centroid wind profile shapes using k-means clustering on the 5000 location training data in 5 PCs space to identify 8 clusters and their corresponding hodograph below. The lowest height point is connected to the origin via a dotted line in each hodograph, indicating the lower end of the profile. Each profile is normalised to 1 at 100 m. The rows and columns share x and y axes, respectively.

Figure 4.7: Cluster representation compared to the original exemplary sample profile using the 80 cluster representation (dashdotted, lower opacity). The matched cluster is indicated in the lower left corner of the sample profile frame. The exemplary sample refers to the wind data on 5th March 2013, 6am at (lat 52.0, lon 5.0) close to the met mast Cabauw (Netherlands).

Some of the wind profile shapes identified with the 80 cluster approach cannot be distinguished by eye when scaled to the 1 at 100 m, but they do differ in their respective scale factors.

As already indicated in fig. 4.4, the sample vertical wind profile is reconstructed from its clustering representation using the matched cluster label and the sample specific backscaling factor for the cluster wind profile shape. An exemplary comparison between original sample profile and clustering representation is shown in fig. 4.7. It is clearly visible that the clustering representation (dashdotted, lower opacity) reproduces the profile of the original sample quite accurately with regards to profile shape as well as absolute wind speed. Quantification of the errors of the representation can be found in sec. 4.3.

4.2 Cluster Wind Resource Representation

In the following, the wind resource representation obtained from wind profile clustering is evaluated with respect to geographical and temporal distributions of clusters and their matched samples on the whole European map.

4.2.1 Geographical Distribution

The correlation between geographical regions and predominant clusters is evaluated by comparing the cluster distributions to a European topological map in fig. 4.8, obtained as the surface geopotential height from lowest level ERA5 geopotential data, see sec. 2.2.2.

The geographical distribution of the clusters is evaluated in two ways, with respect to all samples

1. in each location, see fig. 4.10
2. in each cluster, see fig. 4.9.

In fig. 4.9 the clusters clearly reflect topographical features, when comparing with fig. 4.8. The first 3 clusters and cluster 6 mainly distinguish between different land-sea combinations, while cluster 7 and 8 show most contributions at highest surface elevation sites. Cluster 2 seems to cover the map more evenly, with a focus also on low surface elevation regions also observed in cluster 5, while some higher elevation sites are also included in cluster 4. In an overview:

1. open sea (and Sahara)
2. comprehensive, low elevation landmass
3. coastal regions on the sea (more northern)
4. coastal regions on land, first contribution at high elevation sites
5. low elevation landmass
6. coastal regions on the sea (more southern)
7. medium elevation landmass
8. high elevation landmass

In the open-sea clusters 1 to 3 also the very large lake in the west of Stockholm, Sweden seems to be identified as sea-like, it is only hinted at in the topographical map with lowest surface elevation.

From the location-wise comparison in fig. 4.10, the strong dominance of the first cluster on the open sea is easily observed. However individual sites, especially at higher surface elevation are dominated even by the last two clusters.

Comparing to the wind profile shapes of the individual clusters shows that the most planar profile is found to represent the open sea. Clusters 2 and 5 represent low elevation land mass, where cluster 5 shows more pronounced wind veer and wind shear than cluster 2. The coastal shapes 3 and 4 show similar wind veer with much stronger wind shear on the land mass coastal regions, which can be interpreted as an effect of the landmass slowing down the lower parts of the wind mass. The low-level

jet shape of cluster 6 is matched to coastal sea regions, which hints at their origin lying in temperature differences between land and sea. Clusters 7 and 8 show very pronounced wind veer, with cluster 8 even turning opposite to all other clusters, fitting the image of strong impact of mountainous regions on the wind profile shapes.

Using 80 Clusters

The regional distributions of the 80 clusters are included in the appendix [A.1.3](#), where a splitting up of the 8 regional clusters is observed. For example the first few wind profile shapes are all similar to the first of the 8 clusters with only slight variation mostly visible in the hodograph. The cluster shapes found during the clustering process however differ slightly more, before being scaled to 1 at 100 m. The cluster shapes 1 to 4 are for example scaled by dividing with [1.062, 1.024, 1.106, 1.057] before showing the very similar shapes in [A.1.2](#). These scale factors do not introduce strong differences between the individual shapes, but rather show that there are differences at all, which is not clearly visible by eye.

The regional distribution of these first 4 clusters combined also matches cluster 1 of the 8 cluster analysis. For more difficult regions like the mountainous areas the shape in cluster 8 of the 8 clusters is roughly reproduced by cluster 52, but also more exotic shapes are found, meaning for example clusters 56, 58, 63, 67, 78-80.

This shows that using 80 clusters refines the representation of the wind resource, mostly refining the description of the different regions identified above.

4.2.2 Temporal Distribution and Patterns

Using the full 5000 location data, patterns in the trained 80 cluster parametrisation are evaluated with respect to temporal distribution in years, months and hours as well as wind speed bin and absolute wind direction. Mostly insignificant changes are observed the cluster distributions over different years, but seasonal variation is clearly visible. The first 3 clusters show strong preference for early and late months in the year, while e.g. cluster 12, 13, and 14 peak in summer. Seasonal variation of the wind conditions is thus reflected in some clusters. Over the day the cluster are more evenly distributed, showing only slight increase or decrease mostly at midday.

The wind speed bins highlight that the first clusters predominantly contain samples with maximum wind speed at 100 m in the original data, showing a decreasing trend. The lowest wind speed samples clearly dominate most of the clusters after cluster 55.

Concerning the absolute wind direction of the samples, northern and western wind speeds are observed predominantly, even though the absolute wind direction is not used as direct input to the clustering. The wind direction is projected onto the 100 m wind speed and expressed in terms of parallel and perpendicular wind speeds. The absolute wind direction could thus be implicitly disclosed to the clustering, if it correlates with another feature in the vertical wind profile.

4.3 Validation

The best setup of preprocessing settings, number of PCs and number of clusters and training data is evaluated by comparing the clustering representation with the original wind data. This procedure also gives insight into strengths and shortcomings of the clustering representation.

Figure 4.8: Orientational map showing an estimate of the surface elevation of the European map, obtained from the surface geopotential height of ERA5 [1].

4.3.1 Training and Testing Data

As the clustering representation is to be used to evaluate the complete European map, training and testing data are chosen independently of each other for most of the validation. The training data is chosen to be the 5000 locations shown in fig. 4.1(a) and smaller subsets of the same locations while the resulting representation is compared to 1000 different reference locations shown in fig- 4.1(b).

4.3.2 Difference Types and Selection

The differences are evaluated for each reference sample in absolute wind speeds and also relative to the original wind speed, leading to distributions of absolute and relative errors. These sample wise error distributions are evaluated with respect to their mean and standard deviation, giving information about the bias and the error of the representation, respectively.

Figure 4.9: Cluster frequency at each location with respect to all samples matched to the respective cluster for 8 clusters. The cluster id is given for each frame in the lower left corner. Color ranges are always set combined for each row above the color bar.

These distributions are evaluated overall using different settings for training and preprocessing, meaning different number of PCs, number of clusters and more. Additionally, differences at different heights of the vertical wind profiles and differences for samples in specific wind speed ranges defined by their backscaling are evaluated individually.

The wind resource is represented by parallel and perpendicular wind components after preprocessing, thus these components can in principle be compared individually. However in the later AWE model only the absolute wind speed is considered, therefore the validation is focused on the absolute wind speed only, resulting from the square root of the squared sums of the parallel and perpendicular components.

Figure 4.10: Cluster frequency at each location with respect to all samples of that location for 8 clusters. The cluster id is given for each frame in the lower left corner. Color ranges are always set combined for each row above the color bar.

4.3.3 Differences by n_clusters and by n_pcs

In order to reduce processing requirements, the evaluation for a range of PCs is only run for a subset of 500 locations and the testing data is set as the same 500 location data.

The number of principal components is found to impact the representation error very little compared to the number of clusters used for the representation, as shown for the mean error in fig. 4.11. Considering absolute and relative errors in different backscaling bins the same behaviour is observed in fig. 4.12 and fig. 4.13, respectively.

As a slight improvement is still observable from 3 to 4 PCs, **5 PCs** are chosen for the representation, which is in accordance with the observations and choices made in [10].

Figure 4.11: Mean absolute and relative errors of the clustering representation depending on the number of PCs used. The impact on the mean error is shown for 8, 16 and 80 clusters in (a), (b) and (c), respectively.

4.3.4 Differences by Backscaling Bin

Velocity dependence of the representation error is found comparing the errors for different backscaling values for the chosen settings of 5 PCs on 5000 locations training samples in more detail, see fig. 4.14. The absolute errors are rather evenly distributed over all wind speed bins, as can be seen in fig. 4.14(a), consequently leading to large relative errors for low wind speed samples, as shown in fig. 4.14(b). Overall outperformance of 80 clusters versus only 8 or 16 clusters with respect to error standard deviation is observed. As discussed in sec. 2.1.4, AWES are bound by cut-in and cut-out wind speeds, only within those bounds power can be harvested. For the simulated prototype this exceeds at least 5 m s^{-1} , thus the very large errors for low backscaling values are accepted with little problem.

4.3.5 Differences by Number of Training Locations

Comparing the validation results for a different number of training locations is meant to find optimal choices for training data, however as visible in fig. 4.15 the number of training locations does not visibly impact the observed errors. Therefore one could conclude that training on only 500 locations is enough to obtain good results, however the validation data also only contains 1000 locations such that valid prediction to the full European map is not necessarily ensured. Comparing the 80 cluster

Figure 4.12: Mean absolute errors of the clustering representation depending on the number of PCs used, binned by different backscaling values. The impact on the absolute error is shown for 8, 16 and 80 clusters in (a), (b) and (c), respectively.

shapes for the different numbers of training locations one can still observe change from 1000 to 5000 training locations in contrast to the 8 cluster analysis, where all cluster shapes are equal for more than 200 training locations. Therefore more representiveness is assumed for the 5000 training locations, and thus the setup **80 clusters, 5PCs, 5000 training locations** is chosen.

4.3.6 Differences by Height

Comparison of the reconstruction error for all heights of the vertical wind profile is shown in fig. 4.16, also indicating the impact of the complete clustering representation and only the PCA representation. Even though the PCA is also performed on the preprocessed training data with no low-wind-speed samples, absolute and relative errors are rather similar, especially when comparing to the clustering representation. Here the absolute errors are overall slightly higher than for the PCA, however the relative errors are doubled or even tripled. Hence the clustering representation atherefore the number of clusters is what impacts the performance of the representation most.

The absolute error of individual heights is higher for lowest and highest heights, but shows no strong outliers, see fig. 4.16(a), while relative errors are highest for the lower altitudes, where also

Figure 4.13: Mean relative errors of the clustering representation depending on the number of PCs used, binned by different backscaling values. The impact on the relative error is shown for 8, 16 and 80 clusters in (a), (b) and (c), respectively.

Figure 4.14: Mean absolute (a) and relative (b) errors of the clustering representation depending on the number of clusters, binned by different backscaling values. The impact on the error is shown for 8, 16 and 80 clusters training on the 5000 training locations and testing with the 1000 reference locations.

Figure 4.15: Mean absolute (a) and relative (b) errors of the clustering representation depending on the number of clusters, for different numbers of training locations, all subsets of the 5000 training locations. The impact on the error is shown for 8, 16 and 80 clusters, always using 5 PCs.

Figure 4.16: Mean absolute (a) and relative (b) errors of the clustering representation for the different altitudes of the vertical wind profiles, using 5000 training locations, 80 clusters and 5 PCs. The validation results for using 5 PCs without clustering are shown in blue, with clustering in orange. Overall mean and standard deviation are indicated in the top right of the frame for direct comparability between both cases.

more impact of lower wind speeds is expected, see fig. 4.16(b).

4.3.7 Clustering Uncertainty

Using the chosen setup, the differences for all locations are determined in order to obtain an overall representation error map, see fig. 4.17 and fig. 4.18 for the resulting absolute and relative errors, respectively. In each figure both the resulting maps for the mean the error distribution and its standard deviation are shown next to each other. In the relative difference standard deviation plots, see fig. 4.18(b) no contour lines are plotted, as the small dots of large standard deviation throughout the map lead to a lot of small contour lines making the map hampering readability.

The green color is used to show overflow locations, meaning locations with a much larger error

than most others, which would strongly impact the readability of the color scale if not caught in this way. The overflow is mostly caused from low wind speed samples introducing very high relative errors, as visible in fig. 4.18 mostly in the mountainous regions identified also during geographical analysis in sec. 4.2.1.

From fig. 4.17(a) can be concluded that over most of the European map the wind speeds are slightly overestimated, with a bias of around 0.05 m s^{-1} and a standard deviation showing variation of about 0.5 m s^{-1} . Comparing the standard deviation of absolute and relative errors in fig. 4.17(b) and fig. 4.18(b), respectively, it can be observed that overflow is reached often where the absolute errors are not maximal. This hints again at a strong impact of lower wind speed samples in the relative errors, especially for the identified mountainous areas.

Considering not only absolute wind speeds but parallel and perpendicular wind speeds is also possible in AWERA, but not explicitly included in this work, as only absolute wind speed descriptions are considered relevant. It is however observed that due to the very small perpendicular wind speeds especially there, very large relative errors occur.

The relevant wind speed range for this work starts at a backscaling of 5 m s^{-1} , such that validation maps only for the relevant wind speed range are discussed in the following sec. 4.3.7.

Figure 4.17: Absolute error bias (a) and standard deviation (b) of the clustering representation, using 5000 training locations, 80 clusters and 5 PCs.

Clustering Uncertainty at Higher Wind Speeds Only

The differences for all locations are determined considering only samples with backscaling above 5 m s^{-1} , see fig. 4.19 and fig. 4.20 for the resulting absolute and relative errors, respectively. A strong decrease in relative errors is observed comparing to the full dataset errors in fig. 4.18. Even though the absolute errors are on average slightly larger, the remaining relative errors range between 2% and 20%, with some stronger outliers in the mountainous regions going up to about 70%. Even though overflow handling is still necessary in fig. 4.20(b), no large overflow region is visible as seen in fig. 4.18(b). Highest relative errors are observed in the mountainous regions in northern Africa and the Pyrenees, as well as the Aples. Directly south of the Alpes even higher error contributions are observed on the Po plain in northern Italy, where predominantly very low wind speeds occur.

For a cut-in wind speed of the AWES system as discussed in the following part of at least 5 m s^{-1} backscaling, the clustering representation describes the wind resource available to AWESs with an accuracy rather to the initial ERA5 accuracy, also reflecting the regional uncertainty dependence in ERA5 data.

Figure 4.19: Absolute error bias (a) and standard deviation (b) of the clustering representation, using 5000 training locations, 80 clusters and 5 PCs. Here, only samples with a backscaling above 5 m s^{-1} are included.

Figure 4.20: Relative error bias (a) and standard deviation (b) of the clustering representation, using 5000 training locations, 80 clusters and 5 PCs. Here, only samples with a backscaling above 5 m s^{-1} are included.

4.3.8 Preprocessing validation

The impact of the preprocessing settings on the resource representation is briefly evaluated using the 500 training locations, combining low wind speed cuts and normalisation choices, see fig. 4.21. As observed above, the PCs do not impact the errors when using more than 4 PCs, thus only comparison for 80 clusters is considered. Previous processing results for different numbers of clusters are included but were not evaluated for the highest wind speed bins and therefore show only a horizontal line there. Absolute and relative errors show the same behaviour, when considering wind speed bins, thus only absolute errors are evaluated here.

Using the full number of samples shows improvement in the absolute differences, especially of lower wind speed. However this means including roughly 40% more of the samples in the clustering algorithm than when using the cut. This suggests that the finally chosen 80 clusters are enough to represent the low wind speed samples, while the analysis with only 8 and 16 clusters was more derailed by the additional input. In case of the implementation of AWES with significantly lower cut-in, this evaluation should be revisited, using a more comprehensive set of training and testing locations to

Figure 4.21: Mean absolute errors of the clustering representation depending on the number of Clusters used, binned by different backscaling values. The impact on the absolute error is shown for different preprocessing scenarios, where the data is/is not normalised and low wind speed samples are/are not cut.

see if this improvement holds. However, using more samples in the clustering also makes it more time-consuming.

Leaving out the normalisation from 4.21(b) to 4.21(d) shows an overall increase in absolute errors, especially visible when considering 80 clusters. Using the normalisation is thus still considered a reasonable choice.

The empty 80 cluster results in fig. 4.21(c) suggest that the validation might also be failing at some point here, revisiting the preprocessing validation at a later time is advised.

AWERA: European Power Production Estimation

The AWERA toolchain [53] is meant to provide means for analysis of the wind resource with respect to AWES. It includes power harvesting simulation for AWES for large regions as well as single sites, using the clustering representation defined in [chapt. 4](#) in combination with the QSM. The toolchain concept and resulting AWES operation are evaluated, resulting in estimations of annual energy production for the full European map. The results are validated against sample-wise QSM optimisation, without using the clustering representation.

5.1 Concept AWERA toolchain

In this work wind data for an European map is evaluated using QSM simulation for power production estimation on single vertical wind profiles. The workflow of the AWERA tool is visualised in [fig. 5.1](#), starting at the top left with the clustering procedure for a chosen training data subset. The clustering procedure and validation of the resulting cluster vertical wind profile representation of the wind resource is presented in [chap. 4](#).

In the following, the QSM simulation on each of the cluster wind profile shapes, scaled to a range of absolute wind speeds, the resulting power curves and European power estimation are evaluated. As discussed in [chap. 4](#), the scaling of the cluster profiles is matched by the sample backscaling values, which represent the reconstructed 100 m wind speed of the individual samples. Thus using the backscaling and cluster label of each sample in combination with the power curves, the AEP can be determined for each location of the European map, shown as a result in the bottom right in [fig. 5.1](#).

Using other power harvesting models for AWES is thus also integrateable into the AWERA toolchain, only the power curves need to be updated in this case.

5.2 AWE Power Production Estimation

The power production of an AWES is estimated using the quasi-steady model (QSM) for the Kitepower V3 prototype configuration. Model parameters of the QSM, such as the tether length at which reeling-in is started, are optimized with respect to maximal harvesting power using SLSQP optimization, see [sec. 2.1.4](#).

Figure 5.1: AWERA toolchain analysis flow to obtain a map of AEP for all input locations, starting with a location subset to train the clustering. Similar analysis flows apply to single location analyses. Adding new locations does not necessarily require new training.

5.2.1 QSM Simulation

In the following, the QSM simulation model parameters, handling and impact are discussed. The resulting cut-in and cut-out situations of the QSM are estimated, described by their respective reference wind speeds. The simulation code is provided by Schelbergen [10] as an implementation of the QSM by Van der Vlugt et. al. [9].

Operation

Operational parameters such as azimuth and course angle are given in tab. 2.1 together with the system parameters of the used kite system parameters. The minimal tether length is set to 200 m, thus restricting the tether lengths at the beginning of reel-out and the end of transition phase. In this work, the following parameters are adapted to different wind conditions:

Reel-out and reel-in forces applied to the tether are strong controls on the respective phase durations and cycle trajectories, thus strongly impacting the resulting overall mean cycle power. When choosing the reel-in force, balance between fastest retraction and minimal energy consumption. On the other hand, during reel-out it is favorable to spend more time in energy production relative to the overall cycle duration while at high reel-out force to produce the maximum amount of power. As the reel-out force is limited, wind speeds that would lead to more than maximal reel-out force are compensated by increasing the *elevation angle*, see sec. 2.1.4. A last defining factor is the maximal tether length at the end of the reel-out phase, called the reel-in tether length, which in combination with the minimal tether length gives the effective *pumping length* of the trajectory.

Number of Crosswind Patterns

The simulation includes determining the number of crosswind patterns flown during traction phase. This allows to check consistency with real flight operation, as at least one completed crosswind pattern is expected. The calculation is based on the length of a figure-of-eight Lissajous pattern on a unit sphere, scaled by the tether length to match the flight length of the AWES in the air. This pattern length divided by the tangential wind speed of the system gives the estimated average pattern duration. Dividing the duration of the traction phase by the average pattern duration thus gives an estimate on the number of crosswind patterns flown during traction.

Simulation Results

The QSM simulation results are in part used for further evaluation as they are mostly available for all three phases individually and where applicable for the whole cycle (marked with *):

- average power* [W]
- minimal tether force [N]
- maximal tether force [N]
- minimal reeling speed** [m/s]
- maximal reeling speed** [m/s]
- duration* [s]

The reeling speed results (marked with **) do not contain results for the transition phase, as the phase is meant to have zero reeling speed. Furthermore, the estimated number of crosswind patterns flown during traction, minimal height of flight and maximal elevation angle are included in the QSM simulation results. The relative time spent in traction, called duty cycle, as well as the pumping efficiency, given as the ratio of total energy divided by traction energy, show the performance of the AWES in the QSM simulation. The kartesian x , y and z coordinates of the kite during the pumping cycle are included as kinematics.

Power Curve Simulation

For a given vertical wind profile power curves are found by scaling the vertical wind profile by a scale factor to 65 different reference wind speeds at reference height, each time running the QSM simulation and extracting the average power of the cycle, the so-called mean cycle power. The reference height of 100 m already set in the clustering representation is continued, such that following from the normalisation to 1 at 100 m for the cluster shapes, the scaling parameter directly corresponds to the 100 m wind speed of the cluster $v_{w,100m}$. In conclusion, the power curve for a cluster is given as the resulting mean cycle powers depending on the set $v_{w,100m}$.

For this model the mean cycle power does not contain effects of conversion loss and therefore gives not an electrical but a mechanical power. To give an estimate of the resulting electrical power the mechanical power is scaled by a rough estimate of 90% conversion efficiency.

Cut-in/out Wind Speeds

The range of the scaling parameter $v_{w,100m}$ used for the power curves is estimated by defining a cut-in and cut-out wind speed, only evaluating the power curve within this set range.

Parameter	Lower Bound	Upper Bound	initial value
reel-out force	300 N	5 000 N	minimal force at cut-in
reel-in force	300 N	5 000 N	300 N
reel-out elevation angle	25 °	60 °	25 °
pumping length	150 m	250 m	150 m

Table 5.1: Operational parameter bounds for the SLSQP optimisation to find optimal QSM parameters resulting in maximal mean cycle power. The bounds for reel-in/out force result from tab. 2.1. A lower bound on the tether force is set to always ensure a tensioned tether, as required for operation of a soft kite. The last column contains the initial parameters for the optimisation of the lowest wind speed of the power curve. All values are adopted from [10].

The cut-in wind speed is found by iterating through the lower range $v_{w,100\text{m}} \geq 4 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and choosing the lowest wind speed where steady equilibrium states are found along the entire traction path, setting minimal allowable reel-out speed, defined in tab. 2.1.

Traction in the pumping cycle should be long enough to at least complete one figure-of-eight crosswind pattern, which is not achieved for very high wind speeds. Thus the cut-out wind speed is determined iteratively when flying at maximal elevation angle of 60 °, starting at $v_{w,100\text{m}} = 25 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and increasing $v_{w,100\text{m}}$ until the number of crosswind patterns subceeds one.

The estimation is run with relaxed QSM errors, such that the resulting range of the power curve is expected to be smaller than the estimated cut-in/out wind speeds, resulting in a refined cut-in/out wind speed range.

5.2.2 SLSQP Optimization

The goal for the SLSQP optimization is setting the best operational parameters for the QSM to obtain maximal mean cycle power from a working QSM simulation for any given vertical wind profile, especially for each wind speed of the power curve.

The optimization code is provided by M. Schelbergen [10] and was updated to use pyOptSparse [27] and to be more robust in finding optimal QSM operational parameters for different vertical wind profiles.

Variable Operational Parameters and Bounds

The optimisation is performed on the parameters discussed in sec. 5.2.1, within the bounds shown in tab. 5.1. In principle also the tether length at the start of traction can be optimised, but this parameter is not changed during optimisation in this work as in [10], kept at 200 m. In [10] the optimisation parameters were adapted to perform better for different wind conditions, such that in the resulting optimisation code for wind speeds below 7 m s^{-1} the upper bound for the elevation angle is reduced to 30 °, which is also adopted in this work. Starting at lower wind speeds, the resulting operational parameters are used as initial parameters of the optimisation of the next wind speed step. This already strongly improves the reliability of the optimisation. The first column in tab. 5.1 gives an overview of all parameters of the optimisation, further denoted as x_0 , and the last column gives the settings for the first initial parameters.

Objective Function and Constraints

The SLSQP optimisation method minimises an objective function while adhering to set constraints. The objective function obj is given by the negative of the average cycle power normalised to the wind power density at 100 m, estimated using the barometric air density, times the kite projected area:

$$obj = -\frac{\text{mean cycle power}}{100 \text{ m wind power density} \cdot \text{kite projected area}}$$

Consequently, the minimum of the objective function finds maximal mean cycle power and the objective function corresponds to the power harvesting factor of the system comparing to the 100 m wind mass, see sec. 2.2.3.

The optimisation is constrained by inequality constraints, requiring at least one crosswind pattern, if it can be determined. The maximal tether force can in some cases be exceeded in the simulation, when the tether force control is overruled by the maximum reel-out speed limit, and therefore violation of the maximal tether force is avoided by constraining the negative relative difference between maximal tether force with respect to the tether force limit to be larger than 0.

The remaining two constraints are aimed to avoid large random steps between iterations, encouraging the parameters to continuously reach extremum force values during each of the phases. For some situations, the set maximal and minimal tether force during reel-in/out, respectively, are overruled by the optimisation and thus might not impact the simulation results. The constraints con ensuring more continuity in the optimisation in these situations are given by requiring that the resulting reeling force after QSM simulation compared to the initially set reeling force parameter does not decrease significantly

$$con = (\text{QSM reeling force} - \text{parameter reeling force}) \cdot 0.01$$

for both maximal tether force during reel-in and minimal tether force during reel-out.

The optimisation requires all constraints to be fulfilled, meaning in this case to be ≥ 0 , within the tolerance set to 10^{-6} . In their computation, all constraints are increased by adding 10^{-6} to them, however the concept does not change due to this step.

Robustness

The robustness of the optimisation had to be improved for the use with an arbitrary number of clusters, as some cluster shapes and scaling wind speeds otherwise lead to only very short wind speed ranges with successful simulation results. The robustness of the optimisation was increased by testing varying initial values (x_0) as well as attempting failed simulations for slightly higher scaling wind speeds $v_{w,100m}$.

Smearing x_0

The initial parameters are smeared in total 4 times with each individual parameter being varied in a gaussian distribution with a standard deviation 10% of their original value. In addition, for a more broad random selection a truncated gaussian distribution of the respective parameter bound range is used twice to define the x_0 contributions of each parameter. All smeared starting values are ensured to be within parameter bounds, as defined in tab. 5.1. During optimisation not necessarily all initial parameters are tested as after 3 successful optimisations the maximal power results are chosen to be the final optimisation results for the corresponding initial configuration. This approach reduces the

chance of finding only local minima of the objective function.

Varying $v_{w,100\text{ m}}$

In some cases, the optimisation is unable to produce valid results either due to optimisation errors or QSM simulation errors. For very large and very small scaling values this behaviour is expected, resulting in the cut-in and cut-out wind speeds. However, wind speeds might fail the optimisation but slightly larger wind speeds lead to valid results, especially at the upper end of the wind speed scale. In this case the cut-out wind speed was not correctly reached with the first failed optimisation. Therefore two additional attempts of optimisation are performed, each time performing the optimisation for a wind speed scaling increased by 1/3 of the range to the next wind speed step, or 0.2 m s^{-1} at the end of the range.

5.3 Resulting AWE Operation

The QSM optimisation is performed for both 8 and 80 cluster representations, giving insight not only on the resulting power curves but also the control and kite performance parameter behaviour with changing wind speed. First the resulting cut-in/out wind speeds and power curves are discussed, including the impact of different wind profile shapes. Operational parameters and especially the mean harvesting height are discussed, especially with regard to the impact of the imposed system limits.

5.3.1 Cut-in/out Wind Speeds

The cut-in and cut-out wind speeds are determined from the optimisation results on the wind speed range defined by the estimated cut-in and cut-out wind speeds, giving the starting and end point of the resulting power curve, see fig. 5.2. The figure shows that the cut-out wind speed estimates stringly overestimate the resulting cut-out wind speeds, as some QSM errors are ignored during the estimation process. For some more irregular clusters it was found that the cut-out estimation underestimated the cut-out wind speeds, therefore the cut-out estimation was adapted to reach higher wind speeds. For many of the profiles this however leads to strong increase in processing time, as the most time intensive processing takes place when all fallback wind speeds and optimisation attempts fail one after another.

The cut-in wind speed of the system is relatively high, and in the current implementation the estimated cut-in wind speed is never undercut by the refined results. Reducing the estimated wind speed to 2 m s^{-1} was tested for a few wind profiles, but did not lead to any lowering of the refined cut-in values. Therefore, the cut-in estimation seems to quite accurately estimate the resulting model cut-in wind speed. It needs to be mentioned that the lower wind speeds did often lead to negative mean cycle power results, which are currently not accepted as part of the power curves. However, these results might give interesting input to reverse pumping approaches, meaning the use of power to keep the AWES in the air during short-term wind speed lows.

Comparing to the results in [10], very similar cut-in and cut-out wind speeds are observed for the clusters, overall mostly ranging from 6 m s^{-1} to 14 m s^{-1} up to 20 m s^{-1} .

The cluster wind profile shapes scaled with the refined cut-in and cut-out wind speeds are shown in fig. 5.3 for both the 8 and 80 cluster representations. Both representations show intersections for all cut-in wind speeds for about 80 m altitude and roughly 6 m s^{-1} wind speed and for all cut-out wind speeds between 250 and 300 m altitude and roughly 20 m s^{-1} wind speed. This coincides with the findings in [10]. There the cut-in intersection at 80 m was interpreted as the kite height at the

Figure 5.2: Cut-in/out wind speed estimates and the resulting refined limits after running the full power curve optimisation, for both the 8 cluster and 80 cluster representations in frame (a) and (b), respectively. In frame (b) only the first 8 of 80 profiles are labeled to improve readability and as there is no real information gain when providing all labels.

beginning of the traction phase at lowest possible elevation angle and low winds, thus making the start of the reel-out phase the decisive criterion for cut-in. Similarly, the cut-out intersection is found at the maximum kite height. The 80 m and 300 m wind speeds at cut-in and cut-out could therefore be interpreted as system cut-in and cut-out wind speeds, independent of the cluster wind profile.

5.3.2 Power Curves

From the optimisation on every wind speed scaling step the resulting power curves are given in fig. 5.4 and fig. 5.5 for the 8 and 80 cluster representation, respectively. The resulting mean cycle power of the QSM simulation represents mechanical power. Electrical conversion losses, e.g. from saving and using power in a battery during the pumping cycle, are estimated to lead to 10% power loss. Therefore in fig. 5.4(b), the mechanical power as well as the 90% efficiency electrical power (dashdotted) are included. For later interpretation this difference is important, however for readability reasons only the mechanical power is considered.

The power curve shapes are discussed focusing on the 8 cluster results in fig. 5.4(a). All power curves for the quite different clusters show rather similar development over the wind speed range, even almost coinciding for the wind speeds between 6 and 8 m s^{-1} . Most profiles show continuous increase up to the maximum power of about 10 kW, then a plateau at maximum power followed by decreasing power until cut-out. The cut-out is observed where the wind speed is too high for the QSM to find equilibrium states within the system constraints, also leading to the kite flying more and more depowered in the decreasing slope leading up to cut-out. Profiles 4 and 5 break off at lower wind speeds than most other profiles and do not show a decreasing slope at the end, indicating other model related issues leading to cut out. The wind profile shapes of all low-power and lower cut-out power curves (4, 5, 7) all show pronounced wind shear with very high wind speeds at higher altitudes, especially shapes 4 and 5, suggesting that the prototype system limits are reached earlier for these profiles. Highest mean cycle power is observed for the almost uniform profile 1 and the low-level jet

Figure 5.3: Cluster wind profile shapes scaled with their respective refined cut-in/out wind speeds after running the full power curve optimisation, for both the 8 cluster and 80 cluster representations in frame (a) and (b), respectively.

profile 6, favouring of low-level jets was also reported in [10].

The 80 cluster power curves show very similar behaviour, see fig. 5.5. A very long downward slope at the end of some power curves (55, 56, 63, 73), all profiles showing even more extreme wind shear and strong high level winds than the 8 cluster shapes 4 and 5, ending still at only slightly lower scaling wind speed $\approx 14 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. This suggests that for extreme wind shear, the system has to depower very early on in the power curve, while for the lower wind shear profiles maximal power is harvested flying at lower altitudes. This behaviour is further assessed considering the resulting operational parameters over the wind speed range, see sec.5.3.3.

Figure 5.4: Optimised QSM power curves for the scaled cluster wind profile shapes in each frame for the 8 clusters parametrisation. The effect of conversion loss to electrical power is indicated in frame (b), where the mechanical power from (a) is scaled by estimated 90% efficiency to the resulting electrical power, depicted as dashdotted lines in (b).

5.3.3 Operational Parameters

The resulting operation for all scaling wind speeds of 3 exemplary cluster wind profile shapes are discussed in more detail, focussing on one uniform (1), one strong shear (63) and one low-level jet profile shape of the 80 cluster representation. Following from the mean operational height of the device, average flight altitudes on the European map are evaluated, and inferring from this the wind speeds at flight altitude are mapped as well.

Wind Speed Dependence

The operational parameter results for the 80 cluster representation for the exemplary profiles are displayed in fig. 5.6 including in each frame the results for uniform, strong shear and low-level jet profiles. Corresponding results for the 8 cluster representation using clusters (1, 4, 6) is included in fig. 5.7.

For all considered wind profiles the reel-out force system limit is reached early on in the wind speed range at 8 m s^{-1} while the reel-in force begins to rise monotonically at about the same wind speed. At this point or delayed up to 10 m s^{-1} depowering via increased elevation angle is needed to stay within system limits. Only for profile 63 of the 80 cluster representation, opposite behaviour is observed, suggesting that for very strong wind shear depowering is achieved more efficiently by flying at lower altitudes after about 14 m s^{-1} scaling. At cut-out all profiles show only one remaining flown crosswind pattern, suggesting that this constraint has a strong impact on the maximal wind speed.

The duty cycle shows best performance of the system at lowest scaling, decreasing from about 70 to 50% with increasing wind speed. For extremum wind speeds at about 18 to 20 m s^{-1} , an increase of roughly 10% is observed. Here a kink in the elevatoin angle is observed to even stronger increase, consequently causing the reel-out speed to start decreasing. Overall pumping efficiency shows very similar trends to the duty cycle.

Figure 5.5: Optimised QSM power curves for the scaled cluster wind profile shapes in each frame for 10 of the 80 clusters parametrisation.

The uniform and low-level jet wind profile shapes show overall similar behaviour, while the strong wind shear shapes show less efficiency and require earlier depowering and cut-out. Thus for the considered AWES, high wind shear is therefore disfavoured compared to the other wind profile shapes.

Kite Trajectories

The flight trajectories of a pumping cycle projected onto a two-dimensional plane of height (z) and horizontal distance (x) are shown in fig. 5.8 and fig. 5.9 for the 80 and 8 cluster representations, respectively. The pumping cycle behaviour is clearly identifiable, starting at lower left corner with the traction phase up to the upper right, meaning maximal tether length. Reel-in is performed flying an arch until back at 200 m tether length, transitioning back to the starting point. The strong increase in elevation angle observed in sec. 5.3.3 is reflected in the trajectories, see especially fig. 5.8(a) and fig. 5.8(c).

5.4 AWERA European Power Harvesting

The QSM optimisation results are used to interpret the cluster representation of each sample in terms of power production. First the matching procedure is explained in detail, combining power curves and cluster frequency distributions resulting in a map of mean harvesting power. This procedure is then applied to determine annual energy production and capacity factors for all locations on the European map. Power estimation and results are always based on the 80 cluster representation of the wind resource.

5.4.1 Energy Production Estimation

Using the clustering representation of a single sample, consisting of cluster label and backscaling wind speed, the QSM mean cycle power for the sample can be inferred from the respective cluster profile power curve, given in fig. 5.5. The power curve value at $v_{w,100m} = \text{backscaling}$ directly gives the power for the chosen sample. A sample with backscaling wind speed that is either lower than the cut-in or higher than the cut-out wind speed of the matched cluster power curve, matches the situation where according to the model no operation is possible. Such a sample therefore produces zero power output.

Cluster Frequency

Evaluating large numbers of samples, either for large timespans or large regions, or both, can make this individual comparison very tedious. Especially when only mean powers are to be estimated and the single time and location point is not directly needed, frequency distributions are used to represent the backscaling and matched clusters of the wind resource.

For each cluster and each location such a frequency distribution is defined. The matched samples are used to fill a histogram spanning the cut-in/out wind speed range of the cluster profile. The histogram entries are then normalised with respect to the total number of samples at the location. This automatically ensures that samples that do not match the cut-in/out criterion contribute with zero power in further evaluation. All European locations can also be summed up, dividing by the

Figure 5.6: QSM operational parameters over the scaling wind speed range for profile 1 (uniform), 63 (strong wind shear) and 75 (low-level jet) in the 80 cluster resource representation. In frames (a) and (b), the respective maximum (\vee) and minimum (\wedge) of the forces are displayed around the QSM parameter result. Frame (c) shows the minimal reel-out speed as line, and the maximum marked by \vee .

Figure 5.7: QSM operational parameters over the scaling wind speed range for profile 1 (uniform), 4 (strong wind shear) and 6 (low-level jet) in the 8 cluster resource representation. In frames (a) and (b), the respective maximum (∇) and minimum (\wedge) of the forces are displayed around the QSM parameter result. Frame (c) shows the minimal reel-out speed as line, and the maximum marked by ∇ .

Figure 5.8: Projected QSM flight trajectories onto the z (height) and x (horizontal distance) for selected wind speeds of the full optimisation range. The trajectories resulting for cluster profiles 1, 63 and 75 of the 80 cluster representation are included in frames (a), (b) and (c), respectively. Minimal elevation and tether length are indicated by a dashed line.

number of locations, leading to an overall frequency as displayed in fig. 5.10. For better visibility, four frequency bins are combined into one in the visualisation.

The powers of the respective power curve are matched to the histogram bin centers, and weighted by the respective histogram height. Summing up all power contributions of all clusters at one location automatically leads to the mean harvesting power at the location.

As already assessed in sec. 4, the first clusters focus higher wind speeds, some even show gaussian-like distributions around wind speeds of 8 to 12 m s^{-1} while the last clusters dominate at lowest wind speed range, which are mostly not included in the power curves. The different frequency shapes match what is also observed in [10], however the detailed distributions strongly depend on the input data and are therefore not compared in further detail.

Average Power

Weighting the resulting power curves of each cluster with their respective frequency distribution for every single location results in mean powers for each location, displayed in fig. 5.11. Highest power production is found in the open sea and the sea at the coast of Denmark. Lowest power production is achieved at the mountainous regions, meaning the Alps, Pyrenees, and Atlas Mountains in northern Africa, mountains in southern Norway and Italy.

Figure 5.9: Projected QSM flight trajectories onto the z (height) and x (horizontal distance) for selected wind speeds of the full optimisation range. The trajectories resulting for cluster profiles 1, 4 and 6 of the 8 cluster representation are included in frames (a), (b) and (c), respectively. Minimal elevation and tether length are indicated by a dashed line.

5.4.2 Annual Energy Production (AEP)

The annual energy production results from scaling the mean power of fig. 5.11 with the hours of a year ($365 \cdot 24\text{h}$), shown in fig. 5.12. The features do not change for simple scaling, therefore the features are the same as observed in sec. 5.4.1. For the flat regions in central Europe an AEP of 25 MW h are estimated, the mountainous regions have an estimated AEP of ≤ 10 MW h and on the open sea up to 50 MW h are frequently observed. This is not a strong contribution overall, comparing to on average 3.25 MW h annual energy consumption in one household in Germany [54]. However the used prototype settings were not designed to yield maximum power, a soon-to-be implemented 100 kW or maybe even 500 kW system in AWERA is aimed to show more realistic and practicable results for the AEP of AWES compared to the 10 kW the prototype system simulation produces.

5.4.3 Capacity Factor (c_f)

The capacity factor gives insight on what power the system harvests compared to its maximal capacity, which can give insight into the potential for AWE harvesting more independent of the power scale of the system, as mentioned in sec. 5.4.2. The maximal capacity of the prototype system, normally referred to as nominal power, is set as the maximum of all power curves. Consequently, the capacity factor results from dividing the mean power of fig. 5.11 with the nominal power $P_n = 10.91$ kW, see

Figure 5.10: Frequency of the clusters matching the power curve wind speed bins, in each frame for 10 of the 80 clusters parametrisation.

Mean Cycle Power

Figure 5.11: European mean power map, resulting from weighting the power curves with their respective frequency distribution.

Figure 5.12: European AEP map, resulting from weighting the power curves with their respective frequency distribution times the hours of a year ($365 \cdot 24h$).

fig. 5.13. A capacity factor clearly below 100% is expected, as the wind conditions are not always favorable, however especially in the mountainous regions discussed in sec.5.4.1 only about 5 to 10% are reached at maximum.

5.5 Validation

The impact of the toolchain procedure on the estimated power and AEP is assessed in this chapter. Error estimated for the power production are derived from comparing toolchain power results to running the QSM optimisation on the original sample profile for select testing samples. The dependence of the resulting AEP for the reference locations on the clustering training settings is another way chosen to assess the clustering toolchain impact.

5.5.1 Power Harvesting Optimization

The power production results using the clustering representation are compared to running the QSM optimisation directly on an original sample profile. The starting parameters of the sample optimisation are set to [reel-out force = 4 100 N, reel-in force = 850 N, reel-out elevation angle = 28.6° (0.5 rad), pumping length = 240 m], estimated as overall mean operational parameters. The single sample optimisation is run for an approximately bi-weekly sample selection on all 1000 testing locations shown in fig. 4.1(b). The testing locations are expanded gradually, in order to fill an error map more densely, including also training locations. The locations are not explicitly defined as they are visible in the maps.

Power Curve Spread

The resulting sample power distributions are split up by matched cluster and separated into velocity bins corresponding to the cluster power curves. The exemplary power curves 1, 63 and 75 of the 80 cluster representation are shown in fig. 5.14 compared to the single sample QSM optimisation distributions. In each wind speed bin, the full range of the single sample power is displayed via a thin line. On top of the first line, 99% of the data, excluding 0.5% at every end, are displayed as slightly bigger bar, attempting to remove outliers due only to the optimisation. The mean of the 99% sample power distribution and its standard deviation are displayed in the center. The single sample power results are not filtered for negative power results, such that here a more comprehensive overview of possible mean cycle power results is given.

Considering first the higher statistics plots for the 8 cluster representation and power curves 1, 4, and 6 in fig. 5.15 shows quite clearly that even though large outliers are observed, the 99% distributions still follow the resulting power curves quite accurately. Still the rather high standard deviations suggest that there is a lot of variation in the samples matched to the cluster, see fig. 5.15(b) as an example. In comparison, the power curves for 80 clusters show overall much less single sample deviation. It has to be taken into account that especially for higher profile numbers, much less statistics are available, such that not all wind speed bins are filled with a lot of data points, making comparison of standard deviations less valid. However, validation is in principle only needed for the parts of the power curve that are also later used for evaluation. This means that even though e.g. fig. 5.14(d) does not show a full range of wind speeds, the most frequently used wind speed regions in the power curve are still validated. Higher statistics can always be achieved by running more single sample QSM optimisations.

Figure 5.13: European capacity factor map, resulting from weighting the power curves with their respective frequency distribution normalised with respect to the nominal power of the AWES.

For profile 1 already a high number of samples contributes to the validation. Here very strong improvement in accuracy is observed when considering 80 clusters instead of 8 clusters, see fig. 5.14(a). Here an unwanted effect of the optimisation can be observed, where many the single sample power results are shifted to 6 kW instead of 9 to 10 kW at the end of the wind speed range. This effect was observed to lessen if the clustering operational parameters were used as optimisation starting parameters and is therefore classified as optimisation error and not something inherent to the model. A possibly similar effect takes place in the 12 m s^{-1} region of profile 1. For comparison the single sample production is rerun using the resulting cluster x_0 as initial values on roughly 200 locations. The very low statistics in higher clusters would have required more production with that focus. Still, profile 1 is included in fig. 5.14(b). Even though this is only a small insight, clearly the aforementioned optimisation errors are not observed here, more statistics would be needed to consolidate this observation.

Therefore the clustering procedure brings a clear advantage to the power estimation, as the resulting optimisation parameters of the previous wind speed are used as initial input for the following wind speed of the power curve. This advantage could be transported to the single sample optimisation via defining lookup tables of good initial values depending on e.g. absolute wind speed of the sample.

European Map Differences

The single sample power results compared to the cluster representation power is evaluated in terms of absolute and relative differences, similarly to the validation analysis for the clustering representation in sec. 4.3.7. The resulting bias and standard deviation of the absolute differences are shown in fig. 5.16 and of the relative differences in fig. 5.17.

The absolute differences indicate that the power output is for the most parts of the European map overestimated, at around 500 W on the open sea and 300 W on the land mass. Some locations in Italy, the Pyrenees, northern France and Africa also show clear underestimation of the power in terms of absolute differences per sample, see fig. 5.16(a). The relative difference bias in fig. 5.17(a) shows more uniform distribution over the whole map, which is interpreted as an effect of the higher powers on the open sea, reducing the relative error. In a similar way the underestimation observed on land for the absolute error is found to be compensated as well, as for most locations, relative bias between 10 and 20% is observed, clearly tending to overestimate only. A tendency to overestimate low-power contributions is hinted at in the power curve spread in fig. 5.14(d). Most extreme bias of differences is observed in the mountainous regions (Alps, Pyrenees, northern Africa and Norway) where the clustering representation in sec. 4.3.7 and ERA5, see sec. 2.2.2, show most uncertainty as well.

Standard deviation of the absolute differences ranges between approximately 1.25 kW on the land mass to 500 W on the open sea. These translate to about 40% standard deviation on the land mass and 20% on the open sea. Again, very high standard deviation is observed for the mountainous regions identified already in the clustering validation. Most confidence can thus be placed in open sea and seaside coastal results.

This validation can be greatly improved using more than bi-weekly samples, and for more locations, which however requires a lot of computing time. More detailed investigation of rather representative single locations or small regions could improve the validation computing effort. These could then be compared to the larger map result, to see if its low statistics strongly impact the results. For comparison, the bi-weekly samples used amount up to about 300 vertical wind profiles per location, compared to the available hourly data of 11 years times 9 thousand hours per year. Uncertainties in

Figure 5.14: The power curves 1, 63 and 75 of the 80 cluster representation are included in frames (a), (c) and (d), respectively. The distributions of QSM optimisation results for single sample vertical wind profiles are shown in their respective wind speed bins: The full range of the data is characterised by the thinnest line. On top, 99% of the data, excluding 0.5% at every end, are displayed as slightly bigger bar, attempting to remove outliers due only to the optimisation. In the center, the mean of the 99% sample power distribution and its standard deviation are displayed in standard '+' shape. The resulting electrical power at 90% efficiency of the mechanical power curve is included as dashdotted line. For comparison the single sample production is rerun using the cluster x_0 as initial values for the optimisation on roughly 200 locations, shown in frame (b) for profile 1.

the QSM optimisation also appear in the single sample production, comparison to the single sample results does therefore not give insight into definite errors compared to reality but provides model based validation.

The impact of lower power samples could be further investigated, especially when comparing with more concurrent AWES performance settings of a 100 kW or higher system. The system performance in the QSM optimisation strongly impacts the power output and therefore also the estimated uncertainties.

The relative uncertainties for AEP, power and capacity factor are all classified by the relative uncertainty of hourly production, as they all are result from one another when scaling with the right

Figure 5.15: The power curves 1, 4 and 6 of the 8 cluster representation are included in frames (a), (b) and (c), respectively. The distributions of QSM optimisation results for single sample vertical wind profiles are shown in their respective wind speed bins: The full range of the data is characterised by the thinnest line. On top, 99% of the data, excluding 0.5% at every end, are displayed as slightly bigger bar, attempting to remove outliers due only to the optimisation. In the center, the mean of the 99% sample power distribution and its standard deviation are displayed in standard '+' shape. The resulting electrical power at 90% efficiency of the mechanical power curve is included as dashdotted line.

parameter. The overall error on the AEP would in principle be described by first calculating the AEP and then doing the comparison. On average, the resulting overestimation is factored in by division with \sqrt{n} , as the validation is performed for $n = 350$ samples in a location.

5.5.2 Clustering Representation: Training Locations

As an alternative to comparing single sample QSM optimisations, the estimated AEP of a location is compared within the clustering framework, using different numbers of clusters and training locations to predict the AEP of the reference location. The reference AEP value for the location is determined using the 8 cluster representation of the location wind resource.

The 5 reference locations are (latitude, longitude):

0. Cabauw (Netherlands) - (52.0, 5.0)
1. Ijmuiden (North Sea Close to Netherlands) - (52.5, 3.25)
2. Lake Constance (Southern Germany, North of Alps) - (47.5, 9.5)
3. Northern Denmark Sea - (57.5, 8.25)
4. Faroe (Sea South of Island) - (60.0, -5.0)

indicated as red dots in the testing locations in fig.4.1(b). They are chosen to represent very different loc

The estimated AEP of each reference location is displayed in fig. 5.18, using 8 cluster representations of each of 5 reference locations and a combination of all, 200 to 5000 training locations and 80 cluster representations of the 200 to 5000 training locations. The last entry reflects the chosen representation settings (80 clusters, 5000 locations) used for the prediction of the complete European map.

From fig. 5.18 shows that the locations differ significantly, meaning the that the representation of a single location cannot be safely used to make assumptions about a different location. Training on 5000 locations does not seem to show a strong impact on the AEP but shows overall slight improvement for the selected locations, which is interpreted in such a way that it can also outperform lower numbers of training locations in more varying conditions.

Comparing the 8 and the 80 cluster representations of the 200 to 5000 training locations, in some locations better description of the single location AEP is obtained using only 8 clusters. This is however not interpreted as the 8 cluster representation being favorable, but the reference single location was also obtained using only 8 clusters. As found in 4.1.4 the 8 cluster shapes do not differ much with different training situations. Therefore the improved agreement between the 8 cluster representations is seen as an artefact of the reference description. A good crosscheck for this would be to predict the reference AEP using 80 clusters or at least significantly more than 8 clusters, and then to compare again. In spite of this advantage, for Cabauw the 80 cluster representation still shows improved performance compared to the 8 cluster representation.

The overall differences in AEP range from 5 to 15% compared to the single location representation. For mountainous regions, represented by Lake Constance, this does not hold, as observed before, suggesting to exclude the identified mountainous when drawing conclusions from the resulting maps.

5.5.3 Missing Sources of Uncertainties

In addition to the uncertainties evaluated above, the QSM itself introduces uncertainties when compared to reality. Comparison to real flight data was presented in [9] for both moderate and strong winds at

Figure 5.18: The eastimated AEP for each of the five reference locations predicted for different settings within the AWERA framework is compared. The reference result is set to the AEP of the 8 cluster representation based on the reference location only, comparison results are shown in terms of absolute and relative difference to this reference case. 8 cluster representations of the other reference locations and all 5 combined are used to predict the chosen location’s AEP as well. Then 8 cluster representations based on 200, 500, 1000 and 5000 are used to predict the AEP of the chosen reference location, followed by the same analysis using the 80 cluster representation of the 200, 500, 1000 and 5000 locations. The last entry (80 clusters, 5000 locations) referc to the chosen representation settings.

Rotterdam Harbour in The Netherlands using a 20 kW system. Validation for more diverse locations and wind conditions would contribute to a more comprehensive uncertainty estimation.

The system description of AWES, especially C_L and C_D are impacted by steering maneuvers and greatly impact the outcome of any power prediction, but are assumed to be constant troughout powered and depowered flight, respectively. Comparison between different systems and comparison to resulty using dynamic modelling could help improve both confidence in the model description and the parameters, see sec. 2.1.4.

Both considerations also play a role when scaling the predicted powers up for larger and thus more

commercially viable systems.

Impact of turbulence in the wind is not considered in the representation, low timescale turbulence might easily not be included in the hourly resolved wind data but could impact real operation of an AWES. Especially when considering AWE wind parks at suitable locations, the resulting wake field and impact on operation has to be considered. An approach at describing such wind farms is described in [4].

5.6 Computational Impact

The computational effort improvement compared to evaluating the wind resource sample by sample is briefly discussed here. The clustering procedure using 5000 locations and 80 clusters currently uses a lot of RAM, as the transition to using memory mapped incremental PCA and k-means clustering is not yet done, meaning all data used for the clustering is read to RAM, a few hundred GB. The read-in of the 5000 locations takes up a lot of the time as well, depending on how many cores are offered to perform read in tasks.

Production time depends again on the number of available cores and also the chosen cut-out wind speed. Testing was in this case performed until very high wind speeds, which strongly increased processing time.

In total, about a week of processing time for clustering and power production are needed on the high performance cluster, however very strongly vary with the number of available cores. Prediction of the remaining locations does not strongly impact the processing resources anymore. This however is what is needed most by the designated end user of AWERA, when all processed parametrisation and pipeline can be provided.

As the production was run on the high performance cluster during a time of issues, no more focus on a detailed evaluation on the processing times is made. A more detailed analysis of the required resources should be included in AWERA, especially after a possible update to fully incremental analyses and after choosing lower cut-out ranges for the optimisation.

There is no doubt that using the resource parametrisation drastically improves the processing time. As one sample optimisation takes about half a minute up to a few minutes depending on how well the sample optimisation goes. Even considering only 30 seconds per sample, estimating the power harvesting of all 11 year samples of one location would take about a month, not using parallel cores. And there are about 23 thousand locations used for the European map.

Results

The European wind resource harvesting of AWES is evaluated using the output from the AWERA toolchain defined in chap. 5. First single locations results are presented, followed by mapping the operational height and the corresponding wind speeds for the full European map. This leads to assessment of the overall performance of the optimised system and its potential to contribute to stable renewable energy systems.

6.1 Single Location

The AWERA results for the reference location set at the Met. mast in Cabauw (MMC) are displayed in further detail. The power harvesting timeline is shown, compared to the concurrent AWES harvesting height and wind speeds.

The AWERA tool provides access to hourly sample optimisation results by matching the sample backscaling and cluster to the optimisation output. The simplest case of this was already discussed in sec.5.4.1, where backscaling and cluster are used to read the estimated mean cycle power off of the correct power curve. For a small chosen example timespan, the resulting power is displayed in the lower frame in fig.6.1. From the optimisation results, as defined in sec. 5.2.1, the kinematics of the pumping cycle can be extracted for each successful simulation, labeled with the respective backscaling, and thus evaluated for any given sample. Average, maximum and minimum of the z -component of the kinematics are used to describe harvesting height of the AWES and the corresponding height range. Using the harvesting height, even the wind conditions can be reconstructed without reading the actual sample again. To accomplish this, the matched cluster profile is scaled with the backscaling factor and then the wind speed at the determined harvesting height is given directly via the profile. The resulting height, wind speed and power timelines are displayed in fig.6.1.

It has to be noted that the power curve wind speeds are discrete values, therefore agreement with the sample backscaling is reached via simple linear interpolation. Where the backscaling falls out of the cut-in/out range the minimal/maximal available height of their corresponding wind speeds are chosen. This assumption of continued flight is made mainly such that the operational timeline in fig.6.1 is more educational. The power harvesting is naturally set to 0 whenever the cut-in/out wind speed bounds are exceeded.

Figure 6.1: Timeline comparing the harvesting height and wind speeds at the MMC with the resulting power production for the reference location. In frame (a) the QSM harvesting height and its corresponding wind speed in the cluster representation of the week of samples is displayed. System height and wind speed bounds are indicated with dashed lines. The wind speed bounds are set as the average cut-in and cut-out wind speeds.

6.2 Harvesting of the Wind Resource

The wind resource and its power harvesting obtained for the simulated AWES are collected below. First the resulting AEP and capacity factor maps are included and their respective uncertainties are discussed. The resulting harvesting of the wind resource is compared to the wind resource potential assessed in chap. 3, especially considering geographical aspects and the optimal harvesting altitude.

6.2.1 Energy Production Estimation

The annual energy production for the AWES prototype is estimated for the complete European map, shown again in fig. 6.2 together with the estimated relative uncertainty when comparing the mean cycle power results for the clustering representation with the power results for individual samples. The overall error on the AEP is overestimation when using the relative uncertainty of hourly production, which is to be factored in by division with \sqrt{n} , as the validation is performed for $n = 350$ samples in a location. The uncertainty estimation does not include model uncertainties for the QSM or the ERA5 wind data, additional uncertainty sources are discussed in sec. 5.5.3. The impact of optimisation shortcomings in the reference single sample optimisation leaves room for improvement, see sec. 5.5.1. From the comparison within the AWERA model representation, a relative error on the AEP of about 15% is estimated, see sec. 5.5.2. Due to large error contributions in all steps of the AWERA toolchain, results on mountainous regions are to be interpreted with care.

Over large parts of the European map the prototype AWES is estimated to harvest at least 20 MWh per year, which could support only about 7 average households in Germany [54]. However, comparing to real life situation requires the system analysis to include down time factors for e.g. maintenance work or landing and restart in wind and weather conditions where the system cannot fly.

Figure 6.2: European AEP map, resulting from weighting the power curves with their respective frequency distribution times the hours of a year ($365 \cdot 24\text{h}$) (a) and the corresponding relative error (b).

6.2.2 Harvesting of the Wind Resource Potential

The wind resource potential was assessed in chap.3, showing the most increase in the available wind resource for AWESs operating at optimal height between 50 and 500 m with respect to a 100 m hub height turbine over the land mass. Especially strong improvement is found in the more mountainous regions of northern Africa, the Pyrenees and Norway. On the more flat land mass the ratio between AWES resource power density and 100 m power density is found to be at least 3, favouring AWE harvesting, see fig. 6.3(b).

The capacity factor of the simulated AWES, see fig. 6.3(a), shows peak performance on the open sea with capacity factors of up to 60%, about 30% for flat landmass and below 10% in mountainous regions. The performance of the evaluated system shows reverse regional distribution to the maximal wind resource improvement for AWESs, comparing both frames in fig. 6.3. This behaviour is however not seen as disfavouring AWE in general, but calling for more recent and viable kite properties, with higher and more efficient power harvesting characteristics.

Figure 6.4: Mean and maximal harvesting height resulting from the QSM optimisation. Heights are interpolated to match the sample backscaling, cut-in and cut-out situations are considered to stay at minimal/maximal altitude.

not land when reaching cut-out, as described in sec. 6.2.1.

Wind Resource at Harvesting Altitude

From the determined harvesting altitudes, the wind resource is reconstructed using the 80 cluster representation, as performed in sec. 6.2.1. Here the impact of the cut-in/out range is examined more closely by evaluating two different situations: Samples that do not lie within the cut-in/out range are masked, the wind resource available during and only during successful flight operation is shown in fig. 6.5. Slight improvement over 100 m wind speeds are observed. However, when considering the wind speeds out of cut-in/out to contribute with 0 m s^{-1} to the distribution, the resulting observed full wind resource for the AWES prototype shows even lower average wind speeds than the reference height. Due to the high cut-in wind speed, the AWES prototype cannot harvest the resource potential that was attested to AWE in chap. 3. The effect is quantified by the system down times described in sec. 6.3.1.

Figure 6.5: Mean harvesting altitude wind speed and ratio with respect to 100 m reference height wind speed estimated from the 80 cluster representation and the QSM simulation. Wind speeds are interpolated in the cluster vertical wind profiles using the determined harvesting altitude and the backscaling for each sample. Cut-in and cut-out situations are *masked*, only flight operation is considered.

Figure 6.6: Mean harvesting altitude wind speed and ratio with respect to 100 m reference height wind speed estimated from the 80 cluster representation and the QSM simulation. Wind speeds are interpolated in the cluster vertical wind profiles using the determined harvesting altitude and the backscaling for each sample. Cut-in and cut-out situations are set to *zero wind speed*, the complete wind resource is evaluated.

6.3 Energy Systems Contribution

AWE is not meant to replace other renewable energy resources but complement them, to build a stable energy system with 100% renewables. For this purpose AWE power estimation provided on a hourly resolution can be used directly as input to energy models, see fig. 6.1(b). A more general evaluation on the contribution potential for the simulated AWES is provided below: First the operational down-times of the system are evaluated to see if continuous operation is feasible. Then the average power over a time window of 24 hours is evaluated, to see whether using smart storage of power could help to continuously provide baseload power. As possibility to complement solar power specifically, this analysis is repeated when considering only night times with little to no sunlight.

6.3.1 Operational Down-Times

The optimised AWES prototype shows very high down times, see fig. 6.7, especially over the land mass, with only small regions below 45%. Best operation is consequently found on the open sea, with 15 to 20% down time. The high down times are mostly caused by low wind speed samples below cut-in of the power curves. This makes very clear that the prototype configuration settings as they are now are not viable for power harvesting, however reaching lower cut-in wind speeds can greatly impact this assessment. The cut-in wind speed of a larger and more recent system therefore plays a large role in its performance assessment.

High cut-in wind speeds can also lead to a system having to land, which introduced start and landing delay in the power harvesting, such effects are however not factored in in this model.

6.3.2 Averaged Continuous Power Supply

Concept

For each hourly data sample the average power over a total of the surrounding 24 samples is calculated, where the specific sample is centered as much as possible within the chosen 24 hours timeline. This sliding window average represents a situation where hours with more power production are used to bridge hours with much lower power production, e.g. via energy storage. Storage and conversion efficiencies are not included in the evaluation and the down times are only considered as contribution with zero power. In reality they could also lead to starting and landing of the system, introducing additional down-time delay.

The sliding window averaged power for each sample is then compared to a minimal power bar, set to 15% of the nominal power of the AWES prototype. The maximum number of consecutive hours where the sliding window average does not pass the bar is counted, giving insight to what would be the maximum timespans requiring power buffering from different sources. To make the results more intuitive, the number of hours is converted to days by division with 24 hours per day.

Nighttime Only

The same analysis can be performed using only samples at night. To define nighttime the night hours including nautical twilight from [55] are taken to be the throughout each one of the twelve months, given in central european time:

1: [17, 7], 2: [18, 7], 3: [19, 6], 4: [20, 5], 5: [21, 4], 6: [22, 3],
7: [22, 3], 8: [21, 4], 9: [20, 5], 10: [19, 6], 11: [18, 6], 12: [17, 7].

Figure 6.7: The down percentage is given for each location by the number of samples out of cut-in/out range divided by the total number of samples of that location.

When comparing to the datetime information in the wind data one hour is subtracted, as the data is provided in coordinated universal time. The inclusive selection of night hours sums up to 129 hours for all months, thus leading to a night length of ≈ 10 hours per day. Therefore, the number of nights below the bar is defined by division with 10 hours per night instead of 24 hours for the daily analysis. The average time window is still chosen to be the 24 surrounding hourly samples, variation here is of course possible, depending on the interpretation goal.

European Maps for Day & Night

The timespans below cutoff for the complete day shed positive light on the potential to use AWE in the European energy system in the central and northern parts of Europe. The most consecutive down times range from below 10 days on the land mass down to 5 or 3 days only on the North Sea and open sea regions, see fig. 6.8(a). And these results are found even though the performance of

the prototype AWES configuration is not close to current commercial systems. Strong outliers are found in the Alpine regions in northern Italy, where almost the full 10 years are reached. The other mountainous regions in northern Africa, Norway and also larger parts of Spain show slightly more moderate outliers.

Considering the 15% as fraction of the nominal power, then in a scenario where roughly seven times the nominal capacity is installed in central and northern Europe, only about 7 days maximum consecutive down time of the system has to be buffered by batteries, or other renewable energy sources. This would however not mean that only seven days have to be buffered followed by a long period of unhindered harvesting, as suggested by the results in sec. 6.3.1. The results still show great potential for more recent systems, such an implementation in AWERA is a very important next step.

The night time only analysis in fig. 6.8(b) shows no strong deviation from the full day results. As night time selection does not significantly impact performance with respect to baseload support, AWES could play a role complementing solar energy production, which is not available at night.

Going further with this type of evaluation, the down time could be compared over a small radius around a location, such that again more power production at surrounding locations could buffer lows at individual locations, transported via the power grid. This could be used to assess the impact of decentralised use of AWES and focussing the use of AWES on more favorable locations.

Figure 6.8: Evaluation of the longest consecutive timespan of 24 hour (24 hourly samples) averaged powers below 15% of the nominal power considering the full data (a) and only night times (b).

Conclusion and Outlook

The wind resource was parametrised using the 8 and 80 clusters as basis for the representation. Both parametrisations showed strong geographical distinction between open sea, coastal, land mass and mountainous areas. Therefore, representative vertical wind profiles can be attributed to resulting regional classifications. The clustering representation is based on uniformly selected training locations, however potential for an increase in accuracy is expected when giving higher weight to locations on the more diverse land mass compared to the open sea.

The wind resource's large potential for AWE power harvesting is confirmed for the updated processing procedure and data resolution. Increase factors of 3 and more over the land mass are found when comparing the power densities for optimally harvesting AWE and conventional wind turbines. Using QSM optimisation on the parametrisation of the wind resource, annual energy production at each location for the full European map is estimated. However, for the simulated AWES prototype, the resulting harvesting efficiency is highest where the assessed potential increase with respect to conventional wind is lowest, and vice versa. In addition, the system overall suffers from a lot of down-time due to its relatively high cut-in wind speed. A strong improvement to the AWERA toolchain will therefore be the implementation of more recent AWES. Such implementation is already being worked on, thanks to the support and input provided by Kitepower. The results for such a system are expected to improve the overall performance of the AWES, and successful implementation would provide means for assessment of the current potential of AWE, using AWERA.

The validation of the power harvesting results provided by AWERA are based on the QSM optimisation, suggested improvements of the initial parameters for the validation could be used to obtain more reliable validation results and additional information on the robustness of the optimisation. With more computing time, larger parts of the map and more individual time samples per location could be validated. This would best be performed, when the aforementioned updated AWES is implemented in the simulation and optimisation.

Mountainous regions proved difficult to parametrise using the clustering algorithm, and consequently also showed largest discrepancies when validating the power harvesting results. Results in these regions, especially the Alpes, the Pyrenees, Norway and northern Africa, are therefore to be taken with care. One option to circumvent these problems would be to exclude such regions from the standard clustering algorithm and defining a representation exclusively for such locations. However, the clustering algorithm was found to show clear geographical feature distinction between clusters, such that an additional region with individual clusters would in principle correspond to just using

more clusters. As the mountainous regions show high abundance of low wind speed samples, training on low wind speed samples as well might improve performance there. In case of implementation of a more efficient AWES with a lot lower cut-in wind speed, the decision to train only on higher wind speed samples likely has to be reassessed. The chosen parametrisation settings were found to describe the wind resource reasonably well, considering only the high wind samples relevant for production most relative errors are below 20%. As for all validation steps strong geographical dependence is observed, no average error is extracted from the validation results.

Two sets of vertical wind profiles were identified, 8 profiles were found to be inherent to the wind resource, independent of the number of training locations above 200. Similar shapes are identified in the 80 profiles used for a parametrisation of the wind resource, and consequently for predicting the results on the whole European map. Here, inclusion of completely different regions in the world would be an interesting next addition. The resulting wind profiles could be compared, finding e.g. continental differences between the dominant wind profiles.

Finally, possible contribution to the energy system was evaluated, assessing the maximum consecutive hours with only 15% capacity factor on a 24 hour average. Here especially for central and northern Europe low down times are observed, highlighting power harvesting with AWE in combination with storage resources to potentially contribute to the continuity of harvested renewable energy. No significant change was observed when considering only operation at night, therefore AWE could complement solar energy especially well. This implementation still ignores possible delay due to maintenance or start and landing phases. Adding the option for reverse pumping, meaning to actively use power to keep the kite flying during very low wind speeds to avoid such delays would be a very interesting addition.

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Glossary

c_f Capacity Factor [%].

AEP Annual Energy Production [MWh/a].

AWE Airborne Wind Energy.

AWES Airborne Wind Energy Systems.

PC Principal Component.

PCA Principal Component Analysis.

QSM Quasi Steady Model.